

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3193–3289

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0030

Cover photo

MAHLI image of a sandstone rock fragment (target name Kilmaluag; long axis about 7.6 cm) and a fin (remnants of a vein, at lower left, protruding from bedrock beneath the sand) among windblown sand and granules. The image was obtained on Sol 3208 and is illuminated by sunlight from the upper left; MAHLI image 3208MH0001900011103022C00.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 3193rd and 3289th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Principal Investigator’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Principal Investigator's notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 3192 and 3289.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA's MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator's Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3192–3289*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 29 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 29 July 2021 through 06 November 2021.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report's period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for weeks, months, and even years after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 3192 through 3289 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI PI and PI's assistants, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3193 – 3289						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Drive toward the Maria Gordon drill site	01 Aug 21	3194	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Bregout and the focus stack images were merged.
	01–02 Aug 21	3195	20	20	0	MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
	03–04 Aug 21	3197	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Vendoire and the focus stack images were merged.
	06 Aug 21	3199	4	51	4	MAHLI imaged the target Gabillou and the ChemCam RWEB window and internal hardware. The focus stack images were also merged.
	08 Aug 21	3201	12	57	0	MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well as the target Nadaillac after DRT.
	09 Aug 21	3202	0	0	4	The focus stack images from Sol 3201 were merged.
	10 Aug 21	3203	4	33	3	MAHLI imaged the target Blis et Born after DRT and the focus stack images were merged.
	11 Aug 21	3204	4	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Rodel and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.
	12 Aug 21	3205	7	58	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Grimshader and Barrackan.
	13 Aug 21	3206	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3205 were merged.
	15 Aug 21	3208	10	49	0	During the day, MAHLI imaged the targets Inaccessible_Pinnacle and Kilmaluag. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	16 Aug 21	3209	0	0	4	MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3927 through 4840 (data from Sols 2935–2993) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. The focus stack images from Sol 3208 were also merged.
	17 Aug 21	3210	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Solway_Lowlands after DRT and the focus stack images were merged.
	18 Aug 21	3211	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Sanna_Bay and the focus stack images were merged.
	19 Aug 21	3212	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Camster_Cairns and the focus stack images were merged.
21 Aug 21	3214	8	48	0	MAHLI imaged the target Newcraighall after DRT.	
	22 Aug 21	3215	6	27	0	Phobos-shine experiment - night imaging that corresponds to the sol 3017 and 3071 "triboluminescence" experiment effort. The Phobos shine experiment included imaging of Phobos in the night sky and imaging of rover hardware plus landscape in a single field of view, to attempt detection of illumination by Phobos at night. The chosen Phobos shine scene included the ChemCam RWEB, Mastcams, and Navcams, on the Remote Sensing Mast (RSM) with the Martian sky and landscape in the background. A day-time image was acquired to show the context. This imaging was repeated at night. In total, the night imaging included dark current images (dust cover closed, focus at motor count 0), three images of Phobos in the sky, and 17 images of the RSM hardware and landscape.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3193 – 3289						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Drive toward the Maria Gordon drill site	23 Aug 21	3216	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3214 were merged.
	24 Aug 21	3217	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Spiggie and the focus stack images were merged.
	26 Aug 21	3219	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Smailholm and the focus stack images were merged.
	28 Aug 21	3221	11	56	0	During the day, MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Saltopus. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	29 Aug 21	3222	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3221 were merged.
Maria Gordon drill site	29 Aug & 01 Sep 21	3224	6	49	8	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Maria_Gordon after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.
Maria Gordon drill site	05 Sep 21	3229	3	6	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Maria_Gordon sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Maria_Gordon sample discard pile and the intended and alternate "Portion Characterization" sites.
	The Maria Gordon sample was extracted using Curiosity's drill on Sol 3229 . The MAHLI was not operated during the period that the drill bit assembly held the sample until sample analyses were complete. The sample held by the drill bit assembly was discarded on Sol 3245 .					
	22 Sep 21	3245	6	13	0	MAHLI imaged the Maria_Gordon sample discard pile, the surfaces surrounding SAM inlet #2, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Maria_Gordon sample drop-offs and the Maria_Gordon drill hole.
	23 Sep 21	3246	7	27	1	During the day, MAHLI imaged the Maria_Gordon Sample Discard Pile. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness and MAHLI also imaged the Maria_Gordon drill hole wall that was investigated by ChemCam. Focus stack images were also merged.
	24 Sep 21	3247	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the Maria_Gordon drill cuttings.
near Maria Gordon drill hole	Solar Conjunction period – No MAHLI Operations between Sol 3248 and Sol 3271 .					
	20 Oct 21	3272	9	83	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Goose_Stone and Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds.
		3273	0	0	7	The focus stack images from Sol 3272 were merged.
22 Oct 21	3274	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the target Acadian and the focus stack images were merged.	
Drive toward the Zechstein drill site	24 Oct 21	3276	10	57	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Joppa_Salt.
	25 Oct 21	3277	0	0	4	The focus stack images from Sol 3276 were merged.
	26 Oct 21	3278	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Wardie and the focus stack images were merged.
	27 Oct 21	3279	4	36	3	MAHLI imaged the target Ashlar and the focus stack images were merged.
	28 Oct 21	3280	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Rhue and the focus stack images were merged.
	31 Oct 21	3283	7	51	4	MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Isle_of_Mists and the focus stack images were merged.
Drive toward the Zechstein drill site	01 Nov 21	3284	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor.
	02 Nov 21	3285	3	25	2	MAHLI imaged the target Dornoch_Beach and the focus stack images were merged.
	03 Nov 21	3286	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Dumbuck and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3193 – 3289						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Zechstein drill site	04 Nov 21	3287	6	49	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Zechstein after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.
	06 Nov 21	3289	3	6	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Zechstein sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Zechstein sample discard pile and the intended Zechstein portion sites one and two.
	The Zechstein sample was extracted using Curiosity’s drill on Sol 3289 . The MAHLI was not operated during the period that the drill bit assembly held the sample until sample analyses were complete. The sample held by the drill bit assembly was discarded on Sol 3301 .					

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH0001580010101221C00

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 000158001

product type
as received from Mars → C00

sequence ID → 000158001

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 0101

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 0122

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → 1C00

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → 00

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is not always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (**Section 6**).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 3193–3289 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 3194, 3195, 3197, 3199, 3201, 3203, 3204, 3205, 3208, 3210, 3211, 3212, 3214, 3217, 3219, 3221, 3224, 3229, 3245, 3246, 3247, 3272, 3274, 3276, 3278, 3279, 3280, 3283, 3284, 3285, 3286, 3287, 3289.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

last update: 02_August_2021

Sol 3194 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Bregout													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3194MH0001900011102656C00	2656	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3194MH0001820011102658C00	2658	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3194MH0002650001102679R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3194MH0002650001102680S00				
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3194MH0001820011102668C00	2668	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3194MH0002650001102677R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3194MH0002650001102678S00				

Sol 3195 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 3195)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm										
	3195MH0007690011102681E01	2681	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm										
	3195MH0007700011102682E01	2682	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm										
	3195MH0007710011102683E01	2683	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm										
	3195MH0007720011102684E01	2684	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 3195)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm										
	3195MH0007690011102685E01	2685	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm										
	3195MH0007700011102686E01	2686	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm										
	3195MH0007710011102687E01	2687	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm										
	3195MH0007720011102688E01	2688	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 3195)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm										
	3195MH0007690011102689E01	2689	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm										
	3195MH0007700011102690E01	2690	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm										
	3195MH0007710011102691E01	2691	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm										
	3195MH0007720011102692E01	2692	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 3195)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm										
	3195MH0007690011102693E01	2693	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm										
	3195MH0007700011102694E01	2694	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm										
	3195MH0007710011102695E01	2695	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus		intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm										
	3195MH0007720011102696E01	2696	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

Continued on Next Page...

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 3195)													
mhli00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3195MH0007690011102697E01	2697	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhli00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3195MH0007700011102698E01	2698	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhli00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3195MH0007710011102699E01	2699	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhli00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3195MH0007720011102700E01	2700	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

Sol 3197 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Vendoire													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3197MH0001900011102702C00	2702	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3197MH0002990011102704C00	2704	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3197MH0001930001102737R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3197MH0001930001102738S00							
mhli00299	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3197MH0002990011102714C00	2714	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3197MH0001930001102735R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3197MH0001930001102736S00							
mhli00311	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3197MH0003110011102724C00	2724	14819	3.5	1.6	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3197MH0001930001102733R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3197MH0001930001102734S00							

Sol 3199 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Gabillou

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3199MH0007060011102740C00	2740	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3199MH0001730011102743C00	2743	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3199MH0006260001102796R00			range map product:			3199MH0006260001102797S00		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3199MH0001730011102753C00	2753	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3199MH0006260001102794R00			range map product:			3199MH0006260001102795S00		

ChemCam mirror/window and RWEB

mhl00520	RWEB full frame													
	3199MH0005200011102763C00	2763	13093	22.5	20.6	-1.3	1.4	86.2	4.8	1608	1198	13.9	10.3	
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3199MH0006260001102792R00			range map product:			3199MH0006260001102793S00		
	manual focus on interior hardware													
mhl00520	3199MH0005200041102781C00	2781	12990	28.3	26.4	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	1024	1200	10.9	12.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3199MH0006260001102790R00			range map product:			3199MH0006260001102791S00		

Sol 3201 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHU front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHU contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHU Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)		
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)	
MAHLI calibration target														
<i>Note: one can also use features in these images to determine scale; the scale information presented here is based on motor count, not analysis of the images.</i>														
mhl00371	bar target - 5 cm working distance													
	3201MH0003710011102799C00	2799	14371	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl00372	cent target - 5 cm working distance													
	3201MH0003720011102801C00	2801	14364	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9	
mhl00374	calibration target + front left wheel + surface - 30 cm working distance													
	autofocus on calibration target													
	3201MH0003740011102803C00	2803	12962	30.3	28.4	-2.3	2.6	113.6	8.7	1608	1198	18.3	13.6	
mhl00374	manual infinity focus													
	3201MH0003740021102804C00	2804	12552	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	(infinity)	1608	1198	(infinity)	(infinity)	

APXS calibration target														
<i>Note: one can also use features in the image(s) to determine scale; the scale information presented here is based on motor count, not analysis of the image(s).</i>														
mhl00373	6.9 cm working distance													
	3201MH0003730011102806C00	2806	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	

target named Nadailac - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data														
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3201MH0001900011102808C00	2808	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl00168	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1		intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3201MH0001680011102810C00	2810	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3202MH0001530001102861R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3202MH0001530001102862S00						
mhl00168	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2		intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3201MH0001680011102820C00	2820	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3202MH0001530001102859R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3202MH0001530001102860S00						
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 3		intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3201MH0007050011102830C00	2830	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 4		intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3201MH0007050011102832C00	2832	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 5		intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3201MH0007050011102834C00	2834	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
mhl00743	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2													
	3201MH0007430011102836C00	2837	15161	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3202MH0001530001102857R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3202MH0001530001102858S00						
mhl00168	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1													
	3201MH0001680011102846C00	2846	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3202MH0001530001102855R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3202MH0001530001102856S00						

last update: 10_August_2021

Sol 3203 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Blis_et_Born - after DRT													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3203MH0007060011102864C00	2864	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3203MH0001680011102867C00	2867	14044	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3203MH0001930001102900R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3203MH0001930001102901S00				
mhli00168	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3203MH0001680011102877C00	2877	14046	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3203MH0001930001102898R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3203MH0001930001102899S00				
mhli00743	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3203MH0007430011102887C00	2887	15223	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3203MH0001930001102896R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3203MH0001930001102897S00				

last update: 11_August_2021

Sol 3204 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Rodel

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3204MH0007060011102903C00	2903	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3204MH0001820011102906C00	2906	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3204MH0002650001102929R00				range map product:							3204MH0002650001102930S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3204MH0001820011102916C00	2916	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3204MH0002650001102927R00				range map product:							3204MH0002650001102928S00

REMS UV sensor

mhli00095	standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm											
	3204MH0000950011102926C00	2926	13258	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	65.9	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Grimshader - after DRT**

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3205MH0007060011102932C00	2932	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3205MH0006990011102935C00	2935	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3206MH0002270001102997R00				range map product:					3206MH0002270001102998S00
mhli00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3205MH0006990011102946C00	2946	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3206MH0002270001102995R00				range map product:					3206MH0002270001102996S00
mhli00732	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3205MH0007320011102957C00	2957	14641	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3206MH0002270001102993R00				range map product:					3206MH0002270001102994S00

target named **Barrackan**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3205MH0001900011102968C00	2968	13035	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.6	
mhli00152	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3205MH0001520011102970C00	2970	14213	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3206MH0002270001102991R00				range map product:					3206MH0002270001102992S00
mhli00152	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3205MH0001520011102980C00	2980	14224	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3206MH0002270001102989R00				range map product:					3206MH0002270001102990S00

Sol 3208 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Inaccessible_Pinnacle													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3208MH0001900011103000C00	3000	13043	25.0	23.1	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	1608	1198	15.3	11.4
mhl00297	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3208MH0002970011103002C00	3002	14331	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3209MH0001530001103054R00				range map product: 3209MH0001530001103055S00					
mhl00297	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3208MH0002970011103012C00	3012	14276	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3209MH0001530001103052R00				range map product: 3209MH0001530001103053S00					

target named Kilmaluag													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3208MH0001900011103022C00	3022	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
mhl00297	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3208MH0002970011103024C00	3024	14230	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3209MH0001530001103050R00				range map product: 3209MH0001530001103051S00					
mhl00297	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3208MH0002970011103034C00	3034	14231	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3209MH0001530001103048R00				range map product: 3209MH0001530001103049S00					

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat													
intended working distance to mesh is 12.4 cm; to funnel throat is 16.3 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm													
mhl00312	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 1 of 3 to inspect funnel throat		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3208MH0003120001103043C00	3043	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00312	image focused at mesh		intended distance to mesh: 12.4 cm										
	3208MH0003120011103044C00	3044	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3208MH0003260001103045C00	3045	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 3 of 3 to inspect funnel throat		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3208MH0003260001103046C00	3046	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet													
intended working distance to inlet is ~19 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm													
mhl00228	manual focus		intended distance: ~19 cm										
	3208MH0002280001103047C00	3047	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

last update: 17_August_2021

Sol 3210 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Solway_Lowlands - after DRT													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3210MH0001900011103057C00	3057	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3210MH0001680011103059C00	3059	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3210MH0001930001103092R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3210MH0001930001103093S00				
mhli00168	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3210MH0001680011103069C00	3069	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3210MH0001930001103090R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3210MH0001930001103091S00				
mhli00302	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3210MH0003020011103079C00	3079	14723	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3210MH0001930001103088R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3210MH0001930001103089S00				

last update: 19_August_2021

Sol 3211 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Sanna_Bay													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3211MH0001900011103095C00	3095	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3211MH0001680011103097C00	3097	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3211MH0002650001103118R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3211MH0002650001103119S00					
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3211MH0001680011103107C00	3107	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3211MH0002650001103116R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3211MH0002650001103117S00					

last update: 19_August_2021

Sol 3212 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Camster_Cairns													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3212MH0001900011103121C00	3121	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3212MH0001680011103123C00	3123	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3212MH0001930001103156R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3212MH0001930001103157S00				
mhli00168	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3212MH0001680011103133C00	3133	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3212MH0001930001103154R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3212MH0001930001103155S00				
mhli00743	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3212MH0007430011103143C00	3143	15229	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3212MH0001930001103152R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3212MH0001930001103153S00				

Sol 3214 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Newcraighall - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data															
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3214MH0001900011103159C00	3159	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00168	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3214MH0001680011103161C00	3161	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3216MH0001530001103239R00				range map product:						3216MH0001530001103240S00	
mhli00168	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3214MH0001680011103171C00	3171	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3216MH0001530001103237R00				range map product:						3216MH0001530001103238S00	
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
3214MH0007050011103181C00	3181	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
3214MH0007050011103183C00	3183	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
3214MH0007050011103185C00	3185	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
mhli00743	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3214MH0007430011103187C00	3187	15135	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3216MH0001530001103235R00				range map product:						3216MH0001530001103236S00	
mhli00168	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3214MH0001680011103197C00	3197	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3216MH0001530001103233R00				range map product:						3216MH0001530001103234S00	

last update: 24_August_2021

Sol 3217 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Spiggle															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3217MH0001900011103242C00	3242	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3217MH0001820011103244C00	3244	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
		corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3217MH0002650001103265R00				range map product:					3217MH0002650001103266S00	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3217MH0001820011103254C00	3254	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
		corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3217MH0002650001103263R00				range map product:					3217MH0002650001103264S00	

last update: 27_August_2021

Sol 3219 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Smailholm													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3219MH0001900011103268C00	3268	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00152	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3219MH0001520011103270C00	3270	14044	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3219MH0001930001103303R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3219MH0001930001103304S00				
mhli00152	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3219MH0001520011103280C00	3280	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3219MH0001930001103301R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3219MH0001930001103302S00				
mhli00743	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3219MH0007430011103290C00	3290	15257	2.5	0.6	0.0	0.1	15.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3219MH0001930001103299R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3219MH0001930001103300S00				

Sol 3221 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Saltopus - before DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3221MH0001900011103306C00	3306	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00122	medium-r resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3221MH0001220011103308C00	3308	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7

target named Saltopus - after DRT															
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3221MH0007060011103310C00	3310	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00834	medium-r resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2		3221MH0008340011103313C00	3313	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:	3222MH0001530001103367R00		range map product:		3222MH0001530001103368S00							
mhl00834	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2		3221MH0008340011103324C00	3324	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:	3222MH0001530001103365R00		range map product:		3222MH0001530001103366S00							
mhl00835	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2		3221MH0008350011103335C00	3335	15136	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:	3222MH0001530001103363R00		range map product:		3222MH0001530001103364S00							
mhl00834	medium-r resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 1		3221MH0008340011103346C00	3346	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:	3222MH0001530001103361R00		range map product:		3222MH0001530001103362S00							

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat													
intended working distance to mesh is 12.4 cm; to funnel throat is 16.3 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm													
mhl00312	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 1 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3221MH0003120001103356C00	3356	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at mesh												
	manual focus		intended distance to mesh: 12.4 cm										
	3221MH0003120011103357C00	3357	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3221MH0003260001103358C00	3358	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 3 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus		intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm										
	3221MH0003260001103359C00	3359	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet													
intended working distance to inlet is ~19 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm													
mhl00228	manual focus		intended distance: ~19 cm										
	3221MH0002280001103360C00	3360	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

Sol 3224 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended drill target named **Maria_Gordon**- after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3224MH0007060011103370C00	3370	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00834	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3224MH0008340011103373C00	3373	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3224MH0001530001103424R00				range map product:				3224MH0001530001103425S00	
mhli00834	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3224MH0008340011103384C00	3384	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3224MH0001530001103422R00				range map product:				3224MH0001530001103423S00	
mhli00835	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3224MH0008350011103395C00	3395	15135	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3224MH0001530001103420R00				range map product:				3224MH0001530001103421S00	
mhli00834	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3224MH0008340011103406C00	3406	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3224MH0001530001103418R00				range map product:				3224MH0001530001103419S00	

intended drill target named **Maria_Gordon**- after drill bit pre-load test

mhli00465	context view	intended standoff - 35 cm											
	3224MH0004650011103417C00	3417	12894	36.6	34.7	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.3

last update: 07_September_2021

Sol 3229 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended sample discard site for planned Maria_Gordon drill sample

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3229MH0001900011103427C00	3427	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0

intended portion characterization site for planned Maria_Gordon drill sample

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3229MH0001970011103429C00	3429	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0

alternate portion characterization site for planned Maria_Gordon drill sample

Sequence	Image ID	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3229MH0001970011103431C00	3431	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0

last update: 25_September_2021

Sol 3245 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Maria_Gordon sample discard pile

mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3245MH0001970011103433C00	3433	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00122	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
mhli00122	3245MH0001220011103435C00	3435	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	medium-resolution	intended standoff - 5 cm											
mhli00122	APXS raster spot 2												
	3245MH0001220011103437C00	3437	14059	6.5	4.6	-0.1	0.1	29.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6

SAM sample inlet 2 - cover open - after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter

mhli00779	full-frame using manual focus	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3245MH0007790011103438C00	3438	13080	23.1	21.2	-1.4	1.5	88.3	5.0	1608	1198	14.2	10.6
	full-frame based on 128 x 128 autofocus sub-frame (starting pixel 1008, 768)												
	3245MH0007790031103440C00	3440	13104	22.0	20.1	-1.2	1.4	84.5	4.6	1608	1198	13.6	10.1

Maria_Gordon drill hole

mhli00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3245MH0001970011103442C00	3442	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhli00774	intermediate-resolution view	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3245MH0007740011103444C00	3444	13548	11.2	9.3	-0.4	0.4	46.2	1.3	1608	1198	7.4	5.5

Sol 3246 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Maria_Gordon sample discard pile

mhl00122	medium-resolution APXS raster spot 1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3246MH0001220011103446C00	3446	13914	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0
mhl00122	medium-resolution APXS raster spot 2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3246MH0001220011103448C00	3448	13947	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

intended working distance to mesh is 12.4 cm; to funnel throat is 16.3 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm

mhl00312	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 1 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus	intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm											
	3246MH0003120001103449C00	3449	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at mesh												
	manual focus	intended distance to mesh: 12.4 cm											
	3246MH0003120011103450C00	3450	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus	intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm											
	3246MH0003260001103451C00	3451	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus	intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm											
	3246MH0003260001103452C00	3452	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet

intended working distance to inlet is ~19 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm

mhl00228	manual focus	intended distance: ~19 cm											
	3246MH0002280001103453C00	3453	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

Maria_Gordon drill hole - angled view of wall - night imaging

Note: Determination of range and scale from motor count can sometimes be less accurate via night imaging relative to daytime imaging.

mhl00410	MAHLI pointing ~Southwest- 30° from normal relative to plane defined by top of drill hole												
	3246MH0004100011103455C00	3455	13670	9.7	7.8	-0.3	0.3	40.9	1.0	1608	1198	6.6	4.9
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3246MH0004700001103472R00				range map product:		3246MH0004700001103473S00			

last update: 25_September_2021

Sol 3247 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Maria_Gordondrill hole cuttings

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3247MH0001220011103475C00	3475	13957	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Goose_Stone															
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3272MH0007060011103477C00	3477	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3272MH0007400011103480C00	3480	14220	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103571R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103572S00	
mhli00740	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3272MH0007400011103491C00	3491	14219	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103569R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103570S00	

target named Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds															
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3272MH0007060011103502C00	3502	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00714	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 1														
3272MH0007140011103505C00	3505	14215	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2			
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103567R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103568S00	
mhli00714	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 2														
3272MH0007140011103516C00	3516	14048	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6			
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103565R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103566S00	
mhli00714	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 3														
3272MH0007140011103527C00	3527	14083	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5			
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103563R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103564S00	
mhli00714	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 4														
3272MH0007140011103538C00	3538	13867	7.8	5.9	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	1608	1198	5.5	4.1			
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103561R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103562S00	
mhli00714	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	APXS raster spot 5														
3272MH0007140011103549C00	3549	13971	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8			
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3273MH0001710001103559R00				range map product:						3273MH0001710001103560S00	

Sol 3274 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Acadian													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3274MH0007060011103574C00	3574	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00709	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3274MH0007090011103577C00	3577	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3274MH0001930001103613R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3274MH0001930001103614S00				
mhl00709	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3274MH0007090011103588C00	3588	14014	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3274MH0001930001103611R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3274MH0001930001103612S00				
mhl00715	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3274MH0007150011103599C00	3599	15153	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3274MH0001930001103609R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3274MH0001930001103610S00				

Sol 3276 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Joppa_Salt - before DRT													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3276MH0001900011103616C00	3616	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0001220011103618C00	3618	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named Joppa_Salt - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data													
mhli00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3276MH0007060011103620C00	3620	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhli00763	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0007630011103623C00	3623	13984	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3277MH0001530001103678R00		range map product:		3277MH0001530001103679S00			
mhli00763	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0007630011103634C00	3634	13990	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3277MH0001530001103676R00		range map product:		3277MH0001530001103677S00			
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0007050011103645C00	3645	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0007050011103647C00	3647	13972	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0007050011103649C00	3649	13972	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhli00813	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3276MH0008130011103651C00	3651	14632	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3277MH0001530001103674R00		range map product:		3277MH0001530001103675S00			
mhli00763	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3276MH0007630011103662C00	3662	13971	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
		corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3277MH0001530001103672R00		range map product:		3277MH0001530001103673S00			

last update: 26_October_2021

Sol 3278 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Wardie													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3278MH0001900011103681C00	3681	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3278MH0002990011103683C00	3683	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3278MH0002650001103704R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3278MH0002650001103705S00						
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3278MH0002990011103693C00	3693	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3278MH0002650001103702R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3278MH0002650001103703S00						

last update: 27_October_2021

Sol 3279 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Ashlar															
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3279MH0007060011103707C00	3707	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3279MH0007630011103710C00	3710	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3279MH0001930001103746R00		range map product:							3279MH0001930001103747S00
mhl00763	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3279MH0007630011103721C00	3721	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3279MH0001930001103744R00		range map product:							3279MH0001930001103745S00
mhl00785	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3279MH0007850011103732C00	3732	15063	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3279MH0001930001103742R00		range map product:							3279MH0001930001103743S00

last update: 28_October_2021

Sol 3280 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Rhue													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3280MH0007060011103749C00	3749	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3280MH0007630011103752C00	3752	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3280MH0002650001103775R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3280MH0002650001103776S00				
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3280MH0007630011103763C00	3763	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3280MH0002650001103773R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3280MH0002650001103774S00				

Sol 3283 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Isle_of_Mists* - before DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3283MH0001900011103778C00	3778	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3283MH0001220011103780C00	3780	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named *Isle_of_Mists* - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3283MH0007060011103782C00	3782	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3283MH0007630011103785C00	3785	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3283MH0001530001103834R00				range map product:						3283MH0001530001103835S00	
mhli00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3283MH0007630011103796C00	3796	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3283MH0001530001103832R00				range map product:						3283MH0001530001103833S00	
mhli00794	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3283MH0007940011103807C00	3807	15103	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3283MH0001530001103830R00				range map product:						3283MH0001530001103831S00	
mhli00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3283MH0007630011103818C00	3818	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3283MH0001530001103828R00				range map product:						3283MH0001530001103829S00	

last update: 02_November_2021

Sol 3284 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

REMS UV sensor

standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm												
mhi00095	3284MH0000950011103837C00	3837	13255	16.8	14.9	-0.8	0.8	66.2	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

last update: 03_November_2021

Sol 3285 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Dornoch_Beach													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3285MH0007060011103839C00	3839	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2
mhl00699	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3285MH0006990011103842C00	3842	13929	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3285MH0007030001103865R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3285MH0007030001103866S00				
mhl00699	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3285MH0006990011103853C00	3853	13928	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3285MH0007030001103863R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3285MH0007030001103864S00				

last update: 08_November_2021

Sol 3286 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Dumbuck													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3286MH0007060011103868C00	3868	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3286MH0001820011103871C00	3871	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3286MH0002650001103892R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3286MH0002650001103893S00				
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3286MH0001820011103881C00	3881	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3286MH0002650001103890R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3286MH0002650001103891S00				

Sol 3287 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended drill target named **Zechstein** - after DRT

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3287MH0007060011103895C00	3895	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3287MH0007630011103898C00	3898	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3287MH0001530001103949R00				range map product:						3287MH0001530001103950S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3287MH0007630011103909C00	3909	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3287MH0001530001103947R00				range map product:						3287MH0001530001103948S00	
mhl00801	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3287MH0008010011103920C00	3920	15145	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3287MH0001530001103945R00				range map product:						3287MH0001530001103946S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3287MH0007630011103931C00	3931	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3287MH0001530001103943R00				range map product:						3287MH0001530001103944S00	

intended drill target named **Zechstein** - after drill bit pre-load test

mhl00465	context view	intended standoff - 35 cm											
	3287MH0004650011103942C00	3942	12898	36.2	34.3	-3.2	3.9	134.2	12.4	1608	1198	21.6	16.1

last update: 08_November_2021

Sol 3289 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended sample discard site for planned Zechstein drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3289MH0001900011103952C00	3952	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0

intended portion site one for planned Zechstein drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3289MH0001970011103954C00	3954	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9

intended portion site two for planned Zechstein drill sample

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhl00197	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3289MH0001970011103956C00	3956	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);
15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and

16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 3193–3289 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 3194, 3197, 3199, 3201, 3203, 3204, 3205, 3208, 3210, 3211, 3212, 3214, 3217, 3219, 3221, 3224, 3246, 3272, 3274, 3276, 3278, 3279, 3280, 3283, 3285, 3286, 3287**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{im}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3, Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 91 to 138, then only three of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocusing (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these

values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3194 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bregout - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3194MH0001820011102658C00			
best focus image:	3194MH0002650001102679R00		2679	motor count:		14014	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3194MH0002650001102680S00		2680	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3194	focus merged on sol:		3194	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3194MH0001820021102659C00	2659	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3194MH0001820021102660C00	2660	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3194MH0001820021102661C00	2661	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3194MH0001820021102662C00	2662	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3194MH0001820021102663C00	2663	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3194MH0001820021102664C00	2664	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3194MH0001820021102665C00	2665	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3194MH0001820021102666C00	2666	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3194 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bregout - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3194MH0001820011102668C00			
best focus image:	3194MH0002650001102677R00		2677	motor count:		14015	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3194MH0002650001102678S00		2678	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	1-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3194	focus merged on sol:		3194	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3194MH0001820021102669C00	2669	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3194MH0001820021102670C00	2670	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3194MH0001820021102671C00	2671	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3194MH0001820021102672C00	2672	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3194MH0001820021102673C00	2673	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3194MH0001820021102674C00	2674	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3194MH0001820021102675C00	2675	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3194MH0001820021102676C00	2676	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 06_August_2021

Sol 3197 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Vendoire - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3197MH0002990011102704C00				
best focus image:	3197MH0001930001102737R00	2737	motor count:		14042	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3197MH0001930001102738S00	2738	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	3-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3197	focus merged on sol:		3197	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3197MH0002990021102705C00	2705	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
3197MH0002990021102706C00	2706	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3197MH0002990021102707C00	2707	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3197MH0002990021102708C00	2708	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3197MH0002990021102709C00	2709	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
3197MH0002990021102710C00	2710	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	85	6
3197MH0002990021102711C00	2711	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3197MH0002990021102712C00	2712	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 06_August_2021

Sol 3197 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Vendoire - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3197MH0002990011102714C00				
best focus image:	3197MH0001930001102735R00	2735	motor count:		14027	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3197MH0001930001102736S00	2736	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	3-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3197	focus merged on sol:		3197	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3197MH0002990021102715C00	2715	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3197MH0002990021102716C00	2716	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3197MH0002990021102717C00	2717	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3197MH0002990021102718C00	2718	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3197MH0002990021102719C00	2719	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3197MH0002990021102720C00	2720	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3197MH0002990021102721C00	2721	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3197MH0002990021102722C00	2722	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 06_August_2021

Sol 3197 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Vendoire - ~15 mm standoff							
best focus image:		3197MH0001930001102733R00		CDPID	2733		corresponding frame:	3197MH0003110011102724C00	
range map product:		3197MH0001930001102734S00		CDPID	2734		motor count:	14819	range (cm): 3.5
acquired on date:		3-Aug-21		acquired sequence:			mhli00311		stack type: Relative
motor count interval:		66		merge sequence:			mhli00193		merge type: Basic
acquired on sol:		3197		focus merged on sol:			3197		
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3197MH0003110021102725C00	2725	14555	4.23	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	255	1
3197MH0003110021102726C00	2726	14621	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
3197MH0003110021102727C00	2727	14687	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	191	3
3197MH0003110021102728C00	2728	14753	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	159	4
3197MH0003110021102729C00	2729	14819	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	127	5
3197MH0003110021102730C00	2730	14885	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	85	6
3197MH0003110021102731C00	2731	14951	3.15	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	63	7
3197MH0003110021102732C00	2732	15017	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	31	8

updated: [31_March_2022](#)

Sol 3199 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Gabillou - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3199MH0001730011102743C00				
best focus image:	3199MH0006260001102796R00	2796	motor count:		14031	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3199MH0006260001102797S00	2797	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00626	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3199	focus merged on sol:		3199	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3199MH0001730021102744C00	2744	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3199MH0001730021102745C00	2745	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3199MH0001730021102746C00	2746	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3199MH0001730021102747C00	2747	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3199MH0001730021102748C00	2748	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3199MH0001730021102749C00	2749	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3199MH0001730021102750C00	2750	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3199MH0001730021102751C00	2751	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: [31_March_2022](#)

Sol 3199 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Gabillou - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3199MH0001730011102753C00				
best focus image:	3199MH0006260001102794R00	2794	motor count:		14015	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3199MH0006260001102795S00	2795	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00626	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3199	focus merged on sol:		3199	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3199MH0001730021102754C00	2754	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
3199MH0001730021102755C00	2755	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	223	2
3199MH0001730021102756C00	2756	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	191	3
3199MH0001730021102757C00	2757	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
3199MH0001730021102758C00	2758	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	127	5
3199MH0001730021102759C00	2759	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	85	6
3199MH0001730021102760C00	2760	14195	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	63	7
3199MH0001730021102761C00	2761	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 31_March_2022

Sol 3199 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		ChemCam RWEB window - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3199MH0005200011102763C00				
best focus image:	3199MH0006260001102792R00	2792	motor count:		13093	range (cm):		22.5	
range map product:	3199MH0006260001102793S00	2793	acquired sequence:		mhli00520	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00626	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3199	focus merged on sol:		3199	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3199MH0005200021102764C00	2764	12901	35.83	-3.2	3.8	133.0	12.2	n/a	1
3199MH0005200021102765C00	2765	12925	33.45	-2.8	3.3	124.6	10.6	n/a	2
3199MH0005200021102766C00	2766	12949	31.34	-2.4	2.9	117.2	9.3	255	3
3199MH0005200021102767C00	2767	12973	29.47	-2.2	2.5	110.6	8.2	223	4
3199MH0005200021102768C00	2768	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	191	5
3199MH0005200021102769C00	2769	13021	26.28	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	159	6
3199MH0005200021102770C00	2770	13045	24.91	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.8	127	7
3199MH0005200021102771C00	2771	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	85	8
3199MH0005200021102772C00	2772	13093	22.53	-1.3	1.4	86.2	4.8	63	9
3199MH0005200021102773C00	2773	13117	21.49	-1.2	1.3	82.5	4.4	31	10
3199MH0005200021102774C00	2774	13141	20.53	-1.1	1.2	79.2	4.0	n/a	11
3199MH0005200021102775C00	2775	13165	19.64	-1.0	1.1	76.0	3.6	n/a	12
3199MH0005200021102776C00	2776	13189	18.82	-0.9	1.0	73.1	3.4	n/a	13
3199MH0005200021102777C00	2777	13213	18.05	-0.9	0.9	70.4	3.1	n/a	14
3199MH0005200021102778C00	2778	13237	17.34	-0.8	0.8	67.9	2.9	n/a	15
3199MH0005200021102779C00	2779	13261	16.68	-0.7	0.8	65.6	2.7	n/a	16

updated: 31_March_2022

Sol 3199 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		ChemCam RWEB window - focused on internal hardware - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3199MH0005200041102781C00				
best focus image:	3199MH0006260001102790R00	2790	motor count:		12990	range (cm):		28.3	
range map product:	3199MH0006260001102791S00	2791	acquired sequence:		mhli00520	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00626	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3199	focus merged on sol:		3199	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3199MH0005200051102782C00	2782	12894	36.59	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	255	1
3199MH0005200051102783C00	2783	12918	34.11	-2.9	3.4	127.0	11.1	223	2
3199MH0005200051102784C00	2784	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	191	3
3199MH0005200051102785C00	2785	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	159	4
3199MH0005200051102786C00	2786	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	127	5
3199MH0005200051102787C00	2787	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	85	6
3199MH0005200051102788C00	2788	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	63	7
3199MH0005200051102789C00	2789	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	31	8

updated: 12_August_2021

Sol 3201 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nadailac - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3201MH0001680011102810C00				
best focus image:	3202MH0001530001102861R00	2861	motor count:		14012	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3202MH0001530001102862S00	2862	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	8-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic			
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3201	focus merged on sol:		3202	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3201MH0001680021102811C00	2811	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3201MH0001680021102812C00	2812	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3201MH0001680021102813C00	2813	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3201MH0001680021102814C00	2814	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3201MH0001680021102815C00	2815	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3201MH0001680021102816C00	2816	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6
3201MH0001680021102817C00	2817	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3201MH0001680021102818C00	2818	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 12_August_2021

Sol 3201 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nadailac - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3201MH0001680011102820C00				
best focus image:	3202MH0001530001102859R00	2859	motor count:		14017	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3202MH0001530001102860S00	2860	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	8-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic			
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3201	focus merged on sol:		3202	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3201MH0001680021102821C00	2821	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3201MH0001680021102822C00	2822	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3201MH0001680021102823C00	2823	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3201MH0001680021102824C00	2824	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3201MH0001680021102825C00	2825	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3201MH0001680021102826C00	2826	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	85	6
3201MH0001680021102827C00	2827	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3201MH0001680021102828C00	2828	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 12_August_2021

Sol 3201 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nadaillac - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3201MH0007430011102836C00			
best focus image:	3202MH0001530001102857R00		2857	motor count:		15161	range (cm):	2.7	
range map product:	3202MH0001530001102858S00		2858	acquired sequence:		mhli00743	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	8-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3201	focus merged on sol:		3202	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3201MH0007430021102837C00	2837	15017	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
3201MH0007430021102838C00	2838	15053	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
3201MH0007430021102839C00	2839	15089	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
3201MH0007430021102840C00	2840	15125	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
3201MH0007430021102841C00	2841	15161	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
3201MH0007430021102842C00	2842	15197	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	85	6
3201MH0007430021102843C00	2843	15233	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
3201MH0007430021102844C00	2844	15269	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

updated: 12_August_2021

Sol 3201 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nadaillac - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3201MH0001680011102846C00			
best focus image:	3202MH0001530001102855R00		2855	motor count:		14006	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3202MH0001530001102856S00		2856	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	8-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3201	focus merged on sol:		3202	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3201MH0001680021102847C00	2847	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3201MH0001680021102848C00	2848	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3201MH0001680021102849C00	2849	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3201MH0001680021102850C00	2850	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3201MH0001680021102851C00	2851	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3201MH0001680021102852C00	2852	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3201MH0001680021102853C00	2853	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
3201MH0001680021102854C00	2854	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3203 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Blis_et_Born - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3203MH0001680011102867C00				
best focus image:	3203MH0001930001102900R00	2900	motor count:		14044	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3203MH0001930001102901S00	2901	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3203	focus merged on sol:		3203	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3203MH0001680021102868C00	2868	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3203MH0001680021102869C00	2869	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3203MH0001680021102870C00	2870	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3203MH0001680021102871C00	2871	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3203MH0001680021102872C00	2872	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3203MH0001680021102873C00	2873	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3203MH0001680021102874C00	2874	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3203MH0001680021102875C00	2875	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3203 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Blis_et_Born - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3203MH0001680011102877C00				
best focus image:	3203MH0001930001102898R00	2898	motor count:		14046	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3203MH0001930001102899S00	2899	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3203	focus merged on sol:		3203	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3203MH0001680021102878C00	2878	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3203MH0001680021102879C00	2879	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3203MH0001680021102880C00	2880	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3203MH0001680021102881C00	2881	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3203MH0001680021102882C00	2882	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3203MH0001680021102883C00	2883	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3203MH0001680021102884C00	2884	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3203MH0001680021102885C00	2885	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3203 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Blis_et_Born - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3203MH0007430011102887C00				
best focus image:	3203MH0001930001102896R00	2896	motor count:		15223	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	3203MH0001930001102897S00	2897	acquired sequence:		mhli00743		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	10-Aug-21				merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3203	focus merged on sol:		3203	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3203MH0007430021102888C00	2888	15079	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
3203MH0007430021102889C00	2889	15115	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
3203MH0007430021102890C00	2890	15151	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
3203MH0007430021102891C00	2891	15187	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
3203MH0007430021102892C00	2892	15223	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	127	5
3203MH0007430021102893C00	2893	15259	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	85	6
3203MH0007430021102894C00	2894	15295	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
3203MH0007430021102895C00	2895	15331	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3204 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rodel - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3204MH0001820011102906C00				
best focus image:	3204MH0002650001102929R00	2929	motor count:		14023	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3204MH0002650001102930S00	2930	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3204	focus merged on sol:		3204	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3204MH0001820021102907C00	2907	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3204MH0001820021102908C00	2908	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3204MH0001820021102909C00	2909	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3204MH0001820021102910C00	2910	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3204MH0001820021102911C00	2911	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3204MH0001820021102912C00	2912	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3204MH0001820021102913C00	2913	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3204MH0001820021102914C00	2914	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3204 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rodel - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3204MH0001820011102916C00				
best focus image:	3204MH0002650001102927R00	2927	motor count:		14023	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3204MH0002650001102928S00	2928	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Jan-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3204	focus merged on sol:		3204	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3204MH0001820021102917C00	2917	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3204MH0001820021102918C00	2918	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3204MH0001820021102919C00	2919	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3204MH0001820021102920C00	2920	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3204MH0001820021102921C00	2921	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3204MH0001820021102922C00	2922	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3204MH0001820021102923C00	2923	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3204MH0001820021102924C00	2924	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Grimshader - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3205MH0006990011102935C00				
best focus image:	3206MH0002270001102997R00	2997	motor count:		13990	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3206MH0002270001102998S00	2998	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3205	focus merged on sol:		3206	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3205MH0006990031102937C00	2937	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3205MH0006990031102938C00	2938	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3205MH0006990031102939C00	2939	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3205MH0006990031102940C00	2940	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3205MH0006990031102941C00	2941	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3205MH0006990031102942C00	2942	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3205MH0006990031102943C00	2943	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3205MH0006990031102944C00	2944	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Grimshader - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3205MH0006990011102946C00				
best focus image:	3206MH0002270001102995R00	2995	motor count:		13992	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3206MH0002270001102996S00	2996	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3205	focus merged on sol:		3206	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3205MH0006990031102948C00	2948	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3205MH0006990031102949C00	2949	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3205MH0006990031102950C00	2950	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3205MH0006990031102951C00	2951	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3205MH0006990031102952C00	2952	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3205MH0006990031102953C00	2953	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3205MH0006990031102954C00	2954	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3205MH0006990031102955C00	2955	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Grimshader - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3205MH0007320011102957C00				
best focus image:	3206MH0002270001102993R00	2993	motor count:		14641	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3206MH0002270001102994S00	2994	acquired sequence:		mhli00732	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Aug-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3205	focus merged on sol:		3206	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3205MH0007320031102959C00	2959	14497	4.43	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	255	1
3205MH0007320031102960C00	2960	14533	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	223	2
3205MH0007320031102961C00	2961	14569	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	191	3
3205MH0007320031102962C00	2962	14605	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3205MH0007320031102963C00	2963	14641	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3205MH0007320031102964C00	2964	14677	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	85	6
3205MH0007320031102965C00	2965	14713	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7
3205MH0007320031102966C00	2966	14749	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3205MH0001520011102970C00				
best focus image:	3206MH0002270001102991R00	2991	motor count:		14213	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3206MH0002270001102992S00	2992	acquired sequence:		mhli00152	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Aug-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3205	focus merged on sol:		3206	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3205MH0001520021102971C00	2971	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	255	1
3205MH0001520021102972C00	2972	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	223	2
3205MH0001520021102973C00	2973	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	191	3
3205MH0001520021102974C00	2974	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	159	4
3205MH0001520021102975C00	2975	14213	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	127	5
3205MH0001520021102976C00	2976	14261	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	85	6
3205MH0001520021102977C00	2977	14309	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	63	7
3205MH0001520021102978C00	2978	14357	4.97	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Barrackan - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3205MH0001520011102980C00							
best focus image:		3206MH0002270001102989R00		2989		motor count:		14224		range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:		3206MH0002270001102990S00		2990		acquired sequence:		mhli00152		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:		12-Aug-21				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		48		acquired on sol:		3205		focus merged on sol:		3206			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
				near	far								
3205MH0001520021102981C00	2981	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	255	1				
3205MH0001520021102982C00	2982	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2				
3205MH0001520021102983C00	2983	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3				
3205MH0001520021102984C00	2984	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4				
3205MH0001520021102985C00	2985	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5				
3205MH0001520021102986C00	2986	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	85	6				
3205MH0001520021102987C00	2987	14320	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7				
3205MH0001520021102988C00	2988	14368	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	31	8				

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3208 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3208MH0002970011103002C00				
best focus image:	3209MH0001530001103054R00	3054	motor count:		14331	range (cm):		5.1	
range map product:	3209MH0001530001103055S00	3055	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3208	focus merged on sol:		3209	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3208MH0002970021103003C00	3003	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	255	1
3208MH0002970021103004C00	3004	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	223	2
3208MH0002970021103005C00	3005	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	191	3
3208MH0002970021103006C00	3006	14271	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	159	4
3208MH0002970021103007C00	3007	14331	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	127	5
3208MH0002970021103008C00	3008	14391	4.83	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	85	6
3208MH0002970021103009C00	3009	14451	4.60	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	63	7
3208MH0002970021103010C00	3010	14511	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3208 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3208MH0002970011103012C00				
best focus image:	3209MH0001530001103052R00	3052	motor count:		14276	range (cm):		5.3	
range map product:	3209MH0001530001103053S00	3053	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3208	focus merged on sol:		3209	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3208MH0002970021103013C00	3013	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	255	1
3208MH0002970021103014C00	3014	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	223	2
3208MH0002970021103015C00	3015	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	191	3
3208MH0002970021103016C00	3016	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	159	4
3208MH0002970021103017C00	3017	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	127	5
3208MH0002970021103018C00	3018	14336	5.06	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	85	6
3208MH0002970021103019C00	3019	14396	4.81	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	63	7
3208MH0002970021103020C00	3020	14456	4.58	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3208 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Kilimaluag - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3208MH0002970011103024C00				
best focus image:	3209MH0001530001103050R00	3050	motor count:		14230	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3209MH0001530001103051S00	3051	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3208	focus merged on sol:		3209	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3208MH0002970021103025C00	3025	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
3208MH0002970021103026C00	3026	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	223	2
3208MH0002970021103027C00	3027	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
3208MH0002970021103028C00	3028	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
3208MH0002970021103029C00	3029	14230	5.54	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	127	5
3208MH0002970021103030C00	3030	14290	5.26	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	85	6
3208MH0002970021103031C00	3031	14350	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	63	7
3208MH0002970021103032C00	3032	14410	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3208 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Kilimaluag - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3208MH0002970011103034C00				
best focus image:	3209MH0001530001103048R00	3048	motor count:		14231	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3209MH0001530001103049S00	3049	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	15-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3208	focus merged on sol:		3209	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3208MH0002970021103035C00	3035	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	255	1
3208MH0002970021103036C00	3036	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	223	2
3208MH0002970021103037C00	3037	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
3208MH0002970021103038C00	3038	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
3208MH0002970021103039C00	3039	14231	5.54	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	127	5
3208MH0002970021103040C00	3040	14291	5.26	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	85	6
3208MH0002970021103041C00	3041	14351	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	63	7
3208MH0002970021103042C00	3042	14411	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3210 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Solway_Lowlands - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3210MH0001680011103059C00				
best focus image:	3210MH0001930001103092R00	3092	motor count:		14018	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3210MH0001930001103093S00	3093	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3210	focus merged on sol:		3210	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3210MH0001680021103060C00	3060	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3210MH0001680021103061C00	3061	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3210MH0001680021103062C00	3062	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3210MH0001680021103063C00	3063	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3210MH0001680021103064C00	3064	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3210MH0001680021103065C00	3065	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
3210MH0001680021103066C00	3066	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3210MH0001680021103067C00	3067	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3210 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Solway_Lowlands - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3210MH0001680011103069C00				
best focus image:	3210MH0001930001103090R00	3090	motor count:		14025	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3210MH0001930001103091S00	3091	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3210	focus merged on sol:		3210	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3210MH0001680021103070C00	3070	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
3210MH0001680021103071C00	3071	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3210MH0001680021103072C00	3072	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3210MH0001680021103073C00	3073	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
3210MH0001680021103074C00	3074	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3210MH0001680021103075C00	3075	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3210MH0001680021103076C00	3076	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3210MH0001680021103077C00	3077	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3210 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Solway_Lowlands - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3210MH0003020011103079C00				
best focus image:	3210MH0001930001103088R00	3088	motor count:		14723	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3210MH0001930001103089S00	3089	acquired sequence:		mhli00302		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	17-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3210	focus merged on sol:		3210	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3210MH0003020021103080C00	3080	14603	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	255	1
3210MH0003020021103081C00	3081	14633	3.98	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	223	2
3210MH0003020021103082C00	3082	14663	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	191	3
3210MH0003020021103083C00	3083	14693	3.80	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	159	4
3210MH0003020021103084C00	3084	14723	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
3210MH0003020021103085C00	3085	14753	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	85	6
3210MH0003020021103086C00	3086	14783	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3210MH0003020021103087C00	3087	14813	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3211 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sanna_Bay - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3211MH0001680011103097C00				
best focus image:	3211MH0002650001103118R00	3118	motor count:		14008	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3211MH0002650001103119S00	3119	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3211	focus merged on sol:		3211	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3211MH0001680021103098C00	3098	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3211MH0001680021103099C00	3099	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3211MH0001680021103100C00	3100	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3211MH0001680021103101C00	3101	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3211MH0001680021103102C00	3102	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3211MH0001680021103103C00	3103	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3211MH0001680021103104C00	3104	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3211MH0001680021103105C00	3105	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3211 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Sanna_Bay - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3211MH0001680011103107C00				
best focus image:	3211MH0002650001103116R00	3116	motor count:		14015	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3211MH0002650001103117S00	3117	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	18-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3211	focus merged on sol:		3211	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3211MH0001680021103108C00	3108	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3211MH0001680021103109C00	3109	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3211MH0001680021103110C00	3110	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3211MH0001680021103111C00	3111	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3211MH0001680021103112C00	3112	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3211MH0001680021103113C00	3113	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	85	6
3211MH0001680021103114C00	3114	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3211MH0001680021103115C00	3115	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3212 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3212MH0001680011103123C00				
best focus image:	3212MH0001930001103156R00	3156	motor count:		14043	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3212MH0001930001103157S00	3157	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3212	focus merged on sol:		3212	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3212MH0001680021103124C00	3124	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3212MH0001680021103125C00	3125	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3212MH0001680021103126C00	3126	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3212MH0001680021103127C00	3127	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3212MH0001680021103128C00	3128	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3212MH0001680021103129C00	3129	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3212MH0001680021103130C00	3130	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3212MH0001680021103131C00	3131	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3212 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3212MH0001680011103133C00				
best focus image:	3212MH0001930001103154R00	3154	motor count:		14043	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3212MH0001930001103155S00	3155	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3212	focus merged on sol:		3212	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3212MH0001680021103134C00	3134	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3212MH0001680021103135C00	3135	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3212MH0001680021103136C00	3136	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
3212MH0001680021103137C00	3137	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3212MH0001680021103138C00	3138	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3212MH0001680021103139C00	3139	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3212MH0001680021103140C00	3140	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3212MH0001680021103141C00	3141	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3212 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Camster_Cairns - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3212MH0007430011103143C00				
best focus image:	3212MH0001930001103152R00	3152	motor count:		15229	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	3212MH0001930001103153S00	3153	acquired sequence:		mhli00743	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3212	focus merged on sol:		3212	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3212MH0007430021103144C00	3144	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
3212MH0007430021103145C00	3145	15121	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	223	2
3212MH0007430021103146C00	3146	15157	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	191	3
3212MH0007430021103147C00	3147	15193	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	159	4
3212MH0007430021103148C00	3148	15229	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
3212MH0007430021103149C00	3149	15265	2.53	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	85	6
3212MH0007430021103150C00	3150	15301	2.47	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
3212MH0007430021103151C00	3151	15337	2.42	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3214 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Newcraighall - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3214MH0001680011103161C00				
best focus image:	3216MH0001530001103239R00	3239	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3216MH0001530001103240S00	3240	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3214	focus merged on sol:		3216	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3214MH0001680021103162C00	3162	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3214MH0001680021103163C00	3163	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3214MH0001680021103164C00	3164	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3214MH0001680021103165C00	3165	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3214MH0001680021103166C00	3166	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3214MH0001680021103167C00	3167	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3214MH0001680021103168C00	3168	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3214MH0001680021103169C00	3169	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3214 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Newcraighall - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3214MH0001680011103171C00				
best focus image:	3216MH0001530001103237R00	3237	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3216MH0001530001103238S00	3238	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3214	focus merged on sol:		3216	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3214MH0001680021103172C00	3172	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3214MH0001680021103173C00	3173	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3214MH0001680021103174C00	3174	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3214MH0001680021103175C00	3175	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3214MH0001680021103176C00	3176	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3214MH0001680021103177C00	3177	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3214MH0001680021103178C00	3178	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3214MH0001680021103179C00	3179	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3214 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Newcraighall - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3214MH0007430011103187C00				
best focus image:	3216MH0001530001103235R00	3235	motor count:		15135	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3216MH0001530001103236S00	3236	acquired sequence:		mhli00743		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3214	focus merged on sol:		3216	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3214MH0007430021103188C00	3188	14991	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
3214MH0007430021103189C00	3189	15027	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
3214MH0007430021103190C00	3190	15063	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3214MH0007430021103191C00	3191	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
3214MH0007430021103192C00	3192	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3214MH0007430021103193C00	3193	15171	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	85	6
3214MH0007430021103194C00	3194	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3214MH0007430021103195C00	3195	15243	2.57	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3214 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Newcraighall - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3214MH0001680011103197C00				
best focus image:	3216MH0001530001103233R00	3233	motor count:		13996	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3216MH0001530001103234S00	3234	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3214	focus merged on sol:		3216	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3214MH0001680021103198C00	3198	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3214MH0001680021103199C00	3199	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3214MH0001680021103200C00	3200	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3214MH0001680021103201C00	3201	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3214MH0001680021103202C00	3202	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3214MH0001680021103203C00	3203	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3214MH0001680021103204C00	3204	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3214MH0001680021103205C00	3205	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_September_2021

Sol 3217 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Spiggie - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3217MH0001820011103244C00				
best focus image:	3217MH0002650001103265R00	3264	motor count:		13997	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3217MH0002650001103266S00	3265	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3217	focus merged on sol:		3217	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3217MH0001820021103245C00	3245	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3217MH0001820021103246C00	3246	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3217MH0001820021103247C00	3247	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3217MH0001820021103248C00	3248	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3217MH0001820021103249C00	3249	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3217MH0001820021103250C00	3250	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3217MH0001820021103251C00	3251	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3217MH0001820021103252C00	3252	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_September_2021

Sol 3217 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Spiggie - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3217MH0001820011103254C00				
best focus image:	3217MH0002650001103263R00	3262	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3217MH0002650001103264S00	3263	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3217	focus merged on sol:		3217	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3217MH0001820021103255C00	3255	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3217MH0001820021103256C00	3256	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3217MH0001820021103257C00	3257	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3217MH0001820021103258C00	3258	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3217MH0001820021103259C00	3259	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3217MH0001820021103260C00	3260	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3217MH0001820021103261C00	3261	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3217MH0001820021103262C00	3262	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3219 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Smailholm - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3219MH0001520011103270C00				
best focus image:	3219MH0001930001103303R00	3303	motor count:		14044	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3219MH0001930001103304S00	3304	acquired sequence:		mhli00152	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3219	focus merged on sol:		3219	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3219MH0001520021103271C00	3271	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	255	1
3219MH0001520021103272C00	3272	13900	7.55	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3219MH0001520021103273C00	3273	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3219MH0001520021103274C00	3274	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3219MH0001520021103275C00	3275	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
3219MH0001520021103276C00	3276	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	85	6
3219MH0001520021103277C00	3277	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	63	7
3219MH0001520021103278C00	3278	14188	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3219 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Smailholm - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3219MH0001520011103280C00				
best focus image:	3219MH0001930001103301R00	3301	motor count:		14042	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3219MH0001930001103302S00	3302	acquired sequence:		mhli00152	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3219	focus merged on sol:		3219	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3219MH0001520021103281C00	3281	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3219MH0001520021103282C00	3282	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3219MH0001520021103283C00	3283	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3219MH0001520021103284C00	3284	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3219MH0001520021103285C00	3285	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
3219MH0001520021103286C00	3286	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	85	6
3219MH0001520021103287C00	3287	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	63	7
3219MH0001520021103288C00	3288	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3219 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Smailholm - ~6 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3219MH0007430011103290C00				
best focus image:	3219MH0001930001103299R00	3299	motor count:		15257	range (cm):		2.5	
range map product:	3219MH0001930001103300S00	3300	acquired sequence:		mhli00743		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	26-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3219	focus merged on sol:		3219	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3219MH0007430021103291C00	3291	15113	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	255	1
3219MH0007430021103292C00	3292	15149	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	223	2
3219MH0007430021103293C00	3293	15185	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	191	3
3219MH0007430021103294C00	3294	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	159	4
3219MH0007430021103295C00	3295	15257	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	127	5
3219MH0007430021103296C00	3296	15293	2.49	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	85	6
3219MH0007430021103297C00	3297	15329	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
3219MH0007430021103298C00	3298	15365	2.37	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3221 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Saltopus - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3221MH0008340011103313C00				
best focus image:	3222MH0001530001103367R00	3367	motor count:		14009	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3222MH0001530001103368S00	3368	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3221	focus merged on sol:		3222	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3221MH0008340031103315C00	3315	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3221MH0008340031103316C00	3316	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3221MH0008340031103317C00	3317	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3221MH0008340031103318C00	3318	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3221MH0008340031103319C00	3319	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3221MH0008340031103320C00	3320	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3221MH0008340031103321C00	3321	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3221MH0008340031103322C00	3322	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3221 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Saltopus - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3221MH0008340011103324C00				
best focus image:	3222MH0001530001103365R00	3365	motor count:		14009	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3222MH0001530001103366S00	3366	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3221	focus merged on sol:		3222	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3221MH0008340031103326C00	3326	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3221MH0008340031103327C00	3327	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3221MH0008340031103328C00	3328	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3221MH0008340031103329C00	3329	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3221MH0008340031103330C00	3330	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3221MH0008340031103331C00	3331	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3221MH0008340031103332C00	3332	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3221MH0008340031103333C00	3333	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3221 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Saltopus - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3221MH0008350011103335C00			
best focus image:	3222MH0001530001103363R00	3363	motor count:		15136	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3222MH0001530001103364S00	3364	acquired sequence:		mhli00835		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	28-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3221	focus merged on sol:		3222	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3221MH0008350031103337C00	3337	15016	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
3221MH0008350031103338C00	3338	15046	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3221MH0008350031103339C00	3339	15076	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
3221MH0008350031103340C00	3340	15106	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3221MH0008350031103341C00	3341	15136	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3221MH0008350031103342C00	3342	15166	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	85	6
3221MH0008350031103343C00	3343	15196	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3221MH0008350031103344C00	3344	15226	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3221 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Saltopus - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3221MH0008340011103346C00			
best focus image:	3222MH0001530001103361R00	3361	motor count:		14023	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3222MH0001530001103362S00	3362	acquired sequence:		mhli00834		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	28-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3221	focus merged on sol:		3222	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3221MH0008340031103348C00	3348	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3221MH0008340031103349C00	3349	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3221MH0008340031103350C00	3350	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3221MH0008340031103351C00	3351	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3221MH0008340031103352C00	3352	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3221MH0008340031103353C00	3353	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3221MH0008340031103354C00	3354	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3221MH0008340031103355C00	3355	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_September_2021

Sol 3224 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Maria_Gordon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3224MH0008340011103373C00				
best focus image:	3224MH0001530001103424R00	3424	motor count:		14007	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3224MH0001530001103425S00	3425	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3224	focus merged on sol:		3224	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3224MH0008340031103375C00	3375	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3224MH0008340031103376C00	3376	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3224MH0008340031103377C00	3377	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3224MH0008340031103378C00	3378	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3224MH0008340031103379C00	3379	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3224MH0008340031103380C00	3380	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3224MH0008340031103381C00	3381	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3224MH0008340031103382C00	3382	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_September_2021

Sol 3224 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Maria_Gordon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3224MH0008340011103384C00				
best focus image:	3224MH0001530001103422R00	3422	motor count:		14007	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3224MH0001530001103423S00	3423	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Aug-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3224	focus merged on sol:		3224	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3224MH0008340031103386C00	3386	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3224MH0008340031103387C00	3387	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3224MH0008340031103388C00	3388	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3224MH0008340031103389C00	3389	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3224MH0008340031103390C00	3390	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3224MH0008340031103391C00	3391	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3224MH0008340031103392C00	3392	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3224MH0008340031103393C00	3393	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 01_September_2021

Sol 3224 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Maria_Gordon - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3224MH0008350011103395C00				
best focus image:	3224MH0001530001103420R00	3420	motor count:		15135	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3224MH0001530001103421S00	3421	acquired sequence:		mhli00835	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3224	focus merged on sol:		3224	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3224MH0008350031103397C00	3397	15015	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
3224MH0008350031103398C00	3398	15045	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3224MH0008350031103399C00	3399	15075	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3224MH0008350031103400C00	3400	15105	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3224MH0008350031103401C00	3401	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3224MH0008350031103402C00	3402	15165	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	85	6
3224MH0008350031103403C00	3403	15195	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3224MH0008350031103404C00	3404	15225	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

updated: 01_September_2021

Sol 3224 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Maria_Gordon - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3224MH0008340011103406C00				
best focus image:	3224MH0001530001103418R00	3418	motor count:		14027	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3224MH0001530001103419S00	3419	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Aug-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3224	focus merged on sol:		3224	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3224MH0008340031103408C00	3408	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
3224MH0008340031103409C00	3409	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3224MH0008340031103410C00	3410	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3224MH0008340031103411C00	3411	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
3224MH0008340031103412C00	3412	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3224MH0008340031103413C00	3413	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3224MH0008340031103414C00	3414	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3224MH0008340031103415C00	3415	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 17_March_2022

Sol 3246 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		Maria_Gordon drill hole - looking southwest - 30° from normal - night imaging - all white LEDs on - ~7 cm standoff - merge of images 5-12 of 16											
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3246MH0004100011103455C00							
best focus image:		3246MH0004700001103472R00		3272		motor count:		13670		range (cm):		9.7	
range map product:		3246MH0004700001103473S00		3273		acquired sequence:		mhli00410		stack type:		Absolute	
acquired on date:		23-Sep-21				merge sequence:		mhli00470		merge type:		Basic	
motor count interval:		48		acquired on sol:		3246		focus merged on sol:		3246			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 16				
				near	far								
3246MH0004100021103456C00	3256	13392	13.70	-0.5	0.5	55.1	1.8	n/a	1				
3246MH0004100021103457C00	3257	13440	12.82	-0.5	0.5	52.0	1.6	n/a	2				
3246MH0004100021103458C00	3258	13488	12.03	-0.4	0.4	49.3	1.4	n/a	3				
3246MH0004100021103459C00	3259	13536	11.32	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	n/a	4				
3246MH0004100021103460C00	3260	13584	10.67	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.1	255	5				
3246MH0004100021103461C00	3261	13632	10.08	-0.3	0.3	42.4	1.0	223	6				
3246MH0004100021103462C00	3262	13680	9.54	-0.3	0.3	40.5	1.0	191	7				
3246MH0004100021103463C00	3263	13728	9.04	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	159	8				
3246MH0004100021103464C00	3264	13776	8.59	-0.2	0.2	37.1	0.8	127	9				
3246MH0004100021103465C00	3265	13824	8.16	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	85	10				
3246MH0004100021103466C00	3266	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	63	11				
3246MH0004100021103467C00	3267	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	31	12				
3246MH0004100021103468C00	3268	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	n/a	13				
3246MH0004100021103469C00	3269	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	n/a	14				
3246MH0004100021103470C00	3270	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	n/a	15				
3246MH0004100021103471C00	3271	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	n/a	16				

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007400011103480C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103571R00	3571	motor count:		14220	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103572S00	3572	acquired sequence:		mhli00740		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3272	focus merged on sol:		3273	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007400031103482C00	3482	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3272MH0007400031103483C00	3483	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
3272MH0007400031103484C00	3484	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
3272MH0007400031103485C00	3485	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	159	4
3272MH0007400031103486C00	3486	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3272MH0007400031103487C00	3487	14274	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	85	6
3272MH0007400031103488C00	3488	14328	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	63	7
3272MH0007400031103489C00	3489	14382	4.87	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007400011103491C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103569R00	3569	motor count:		14219	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103570S00	3570	acquired sequence:		mhli00740		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3272	focus merged on sol:		3273	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007400031103493C00	3493	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	255	1
3272MH0007400031103494C00	3494	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
3272MH0007400031103495C00	3495	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
3272MH0007400031103496C00	3496	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	159	4
3272MH0007400031103497C00	3497	14219	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5
3272MH0007400031103498C00	3498	14273	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	85	6
3272MH0007400031103499C00	3499	14327	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	63	7
3272MH0007400031103500C00	3500	14381	4.87	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007140011103505C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103567R00	3567	motor count:		14215	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103568S00	3568	acquired sequence:		mhli00714		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3272	focus merged on sol:		3273	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007140031103507C00	3507	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3272MH0007140031103508C00	3508	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
3272MH0007140031103509C00	3509	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	191	3
3272MH0007140031103510C00	3510	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	159	4
3272MH0007140031103511C00	3511	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	127	5
3272MH0007140031103512C00	3512	14281	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	85	6
3272MH0007140031103513C00	3513	14347	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	63	7
3272MH0007140031103514C00	3514	14413	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	31	8

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007140011103516C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103565R00	3565	motor count:		14048	range (cm):		6.5	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103566S00	3566	acquired sequence:		mhli00714		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3272	focus merged on sol:		3273	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007140031103518C00	3518	13784	8.51	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	255	1
3272MH0007140031103519C00	3519	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
3272MH0007140031103520C00	3520	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3272MH0007140031103521C00	3521	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3272MH0007140031103522C00	3522	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
3272MH0007140031103523C00	3523	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	85	6
3272MH0007140031103524C00	3524	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	63	7
3272MH0007140031103525C00	3525	14246	5.47	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007140011103527C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103563R00	3563	motor count:		14083	range (cm):		6.3	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103564S00	3564	acquired sequence:		mhli00714	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3272	focus merged on sol:		3273	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007140031103529C00	3529	13819	8.20	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.7	255	1
3272MH0007140031103530C00	3530	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3272MH0007140031103531C00	3531	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3272MH0007140031103532C00	3532	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3272MH0007140031103533C00	3533	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	127	5
3272MH0007140031103534C00	3534	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	85	6
3272MH0007140031103535C00	3535	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3272MH0007140031103536C00	3536	14281	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - ~6 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007140011103538C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103561R00	3561	motor count:		13867	range (cm):		7.8	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103562S00	3562	acquired sequence:		mhli00714	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3272	focus merged on sol:		3273	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007140031103540C00	3540	13603	10.43	-0.3	0.3	43.6	1.1	255	1
3272MH0007140031103541C00	3541	13669	9.66	-0.3	0.3	40.9	1.0	223	2
3272MH0007140031103542C00	3542	13735	8.98	-0.3	0.2	38.5	0.9	191	3
3272MH0007140031103543C00	3543	13801	8.36	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	159	4
3272MH0007140031103544C00	3544	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	127	5
3272MH0007140031103545C00	3545	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	85	6
3272MH0007140031103546C00	3546	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	63	7
3272MH0007140031103547C00	3547	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3272MH0007140011103549C00				
best focus image:	3273MH0001710001103559R00	3559	motor count:		13971	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3273MH0001710001103560S00	3560	acquired sequence:		mhli00714		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	20-Oct-21		merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3272		focus merged on sol:		3273
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3272MH0007140031103551C00	3551	13707	9.26	-0.3	0.3	39.5	0.9	255	1
3272MH0007140031103552C00	3552	13773	8.61	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	223	2
3272MH0007140031103553C00	3553	13839	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3272MH0007140031103554C00	3554	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	159	4
3272MH0007140031103555C00	3555	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3272MH0007140031103556C00	3556	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
3272MH0007140031103557C00	3557	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3272MH0007140031103558C00	3558	14169	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

updated: 25_October_2021

Sol 3274 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Acadian - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3274MH0007090011103577C00			
best focus image:	3274MH0001930001103613R00		3613	motor count:		14013	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3274MH0001930001103614S00		3614	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3274	focus merged on sol:		3274	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3274MH0007090031103579C00	3579	13821	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
3274MH0007090031103580C00	3580	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
3274MH0007090031103581C00	3581	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3274MH0007090031103582C00	3582	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3274MH0007090031103583C00	3583	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3274MH0007090031103584C00	3584	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3274MH0007090031103585C00	3585	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
3274MH0007090031103586C00	3586	14157	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	31	8

updated: 25_October_2021

Sol 3274 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Acadian - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3274MH0007090011103588C00			
best focus image:	3274MH0001930001103611R00		3611	motor count:		14014	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3274MH0001930001103612S00		3612	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3274	focus merged on sol:		3274	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3274MH0007090031103590C00	3590	13822	8.18	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
3274MH0007090031103591C00	3591	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
3274MH0007090031103592C00	3592	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
3274MH0007090031103593C00	3593	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3274MH0007090031103594C00	3594	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3274MH0007090031103595C00	3595	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3274MH0007090031103596C00	3596	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3274MH0007090031103597C00	3597	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	31	8

updated: 25_October_2021

Sol 3274 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Acadian - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3274MH0007150011103599C00				
best focus image:	3274MH0001930001103609R00	3609	motor count:		15153	range (cm):		2.7	
range map product:	3274MH0001930001103610S00	3610	acquired sequence:		mhli00715		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	22-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3274	focus merged on sol:		3274	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3274MH0007150031103601C00	3601	14817	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	255	1
3274MH0007150031103602C00	3602	14901	3.26	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	223	2
3274MH0007150031103603C00	3603	14985	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	191	3
3274MH0007150031103604C00	3604	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
3274MH0007150031103605C00	3605	15153	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
3274MH0007150031103606C00	3606	15237	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	85	6
3274MH0007150031103607C00	3607	15321	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
3274MH0007150031103608C00	3608	15405	2.31	0.0	0.1	15.0	0.2	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3276 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Joppa_Salt - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3276MH0007630011103623C00				
best focus image:	3277MH0001530001103678R00	3678	motor count:		13984	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3277MH0001530001103679S00	3679	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Oct-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3276	focus merged on sol:		3277	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3276MH0007630031103625C00	3625	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3276MH0007630031103626C00	3626	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3276MH0007630031103627C00	3627	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3276MH0007630031103628C00	3628	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3276MH0007630031103629C00	3629	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3276MH0007630031103630C00	3630	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	85	6
3276MH0007630031103631C00	3631	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3276MH0007630031103632C00	3632	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3276 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Joppa_Salt - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3276MH0007630011103634C00				
best focus image:	3277MH0001530001103676R00	3676	motor count:		13990	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3277MH0001530001103677S00	3677	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Oct-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3276	focus merged on sol:		3277	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3276MH0007630031103636C00	3636	13894	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3276MH0007630031103637C00	3637	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3276MH0007630031103638C00	3638	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3276MH0007630031103639C00	3639	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3276MH0007630031103640C00	3640	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3276MH0007630031103641C00	3641	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	85	6
3276MH0007630031103642C00	3642	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3276MH0007630031103643C00	3643	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3276 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Joppa_Salt - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3276MH0008130011103651C00			
best focus image:	3277MH0001530001103674R00		3674	motor count:		14632	range (cm):	4.0	
range map product:	3277MH0001530001103675S00		3675	acquired sequence:		mhli00813	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3276	focus merged on sol:		3277	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3276MH0008130031103653C00	3653	14512	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	255	1
3276MH0008130031103654C00	3654	14542	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	223	2
3276MH0008130031103655C00	3655	14572	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	191	3
3276MH0008130031103656C00	3656	14602	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	159	4
3276MH0008130031103657C00	3657	14632	3.99	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	127	5
3276MH0008130031103658C00	3658	14662	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	85	6
3276MH0008130031103659C00	3659	14692	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	63	7
3276MH0008130031103660C00	3660	14722	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3276 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Joppa_Salt - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3276MH0007630011103662C00			
best focus image:	3277MH0001530001103672R00		3672	motor count:		13971	range (cm):	7.0	
range map product:	3277MH0001530001103673S00		3673	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	25-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3276	focus merged on sol:		3277	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3276MH0007630031103664C00	3664	13875	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3276MH0007630031103665C00	3665	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	223	2
3276MH0007630031103666C00	3666	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3276MH0007630031103667C00	3667	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3276MH0007630031103668C00	3668	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3276MH0007630031103669C00	3669	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	85	6
3276MH0007630031103670C00	3670	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
3276MH0007630031103671C00	3671	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3278 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Wardie - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3278MH0002990011103683C00			
best focus image:	3278MH0002650001103704R00		3704	motor count:		14012	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3278MH0002650001103705S00		3705	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3278	focus merged on sol:		3278	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3278MH0002990021103684C00	3684	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3278MH0002990021103685C00	3685	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3278MH0002990021103686C00	3686	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3278MH0002990021103687C00	3687	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3278MH0002990021103688C00	3688	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3278MH0002990021103689C00	3689	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	85	6
3278MH0002990021103690C00	3690	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3278MH0002990021103691C00	3691	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3278 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Wardie - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3278MH0002990011103693C00			
best focus image:	3278MH0002650001103702R00		3702	motor count:		14018	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3278MH0002650001103703S00		3703	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3278	focus merged on sol:		3278	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3278MH0002990021103694C00	3694	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3278MH0002990021103695C00	3695	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3278MH0002990021103696C00	3696	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3278MH0002990021103697C00	3697	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3278MH0002990021103698C00	3698	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3278MH0002990021103699C00	3699	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	85	6
3278MH0002990021103700C00	3700	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3278MH0002990021103701C00	3701	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3279 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3279MH0007630011103710C00			
best focus image:	3279MH0001930001103746R00		3746	motor count:		13992	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3279MH0001930001103747S00		3747	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3279	focus merged on sol:		3279	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3279MH0007630031103712C00	3712	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3279MH0007630031103713C00	3713	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3279MH0007630031103714C00	3714	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3279MH0007630031103715C00	3715	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3279MH0007630031103716C00	3716	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3279MH0007630031103717C00	3717	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3279MH0007630031103718C00	3718	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3279MH0007630031103719C00	3719	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3279 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ashlar - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3279MH0007630011103721C00			
best focus image:	3279MH0001930001103744R00		3744	motor count:		13999	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3279MH0001930001103745S00		3745	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3279	focus merged on sol:		3279	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3279MH0007630031103723C00	3723	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3279MH0007630031103724C00	3724	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3279MH0007630031103725C00	3725	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3279MH0007630031103726C00	3726	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3279MH0007630031103727C00	3727	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3279MH0007630031103728C00	3728	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3279MH0007630031103729C00	3729	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3279MH0007630031103730C00	3730	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3279 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Ashlar - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3279MH0007850011103732C00				
best focus image:	3279MH0001930001103742R00	3742	motor count:		15063	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3279MH0001930001103743S00	3743	acquired sequence:		mhli00785		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	27-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3279	focus merged on sol:		3279	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3279MH0007850031103734C00	3734	14895	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	255	1
3279MH0007850031103735C00	3735	14937	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	223	2
3279MH0007850031103736C00	3736	14979	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3
3279MH0007850031103737C00	3737	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
3279MH0007850031103738C00	3738	15063	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
3279MH0007850031103739C00	3739	15105	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	85	6
3279MH0007850031103740C00	3740	15147	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
3279MH0007850031103741C00	3741	15189	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3280 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rhue - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3280MH0007630011103752C00				
best focus image:	3280MH0002650001103775R00	3775	motor count:		14035	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3280MH0002650001103776S00	3776	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Oct-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3280	focus merged on sol:		3280	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3280MH0007630031103754C00	3754	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3280MH0007630031103755C00	3755	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
3280MH0007630031103756C00	3756	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
3280MH0007630031103757C00	3757	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3280MH0007630031103758C00	3758	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3280MH0007630031103759C00	3759	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	85	6
3280MH0007630031103760C00	3760	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3280MH0007630031103761C00	3761	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3280 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rhue - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3280MH0007630011103763C00				
best focus image:	3280MH0002650001103773R00	3773	motor count:		14039	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3280MH0002650001103774S00	3774	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Oct-21	merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3280	focus merged on sol:		3280	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3280MH0007630031103765C00	3765	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	255	1
3280MH0007630031103766C00	3766	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3280MH0007630031103767C00	3767	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3280MH0007630031103768C00	3768	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
3280MH0007630031103769C00	3769	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3280MH0007630031103770C00	3770	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	85	6
3280MH0007630031103771C00	3771	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3280MH0007630031103772C00	3772	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3283 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Isle_of_Mists - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3283MH0007630011103785C00				
best focus image:	3283MH0001530001103834R00	3834	motor count:		13999	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3283MH0001530001103835S00	3835	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3283	focus merged on sol:		3283	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3283MH0007630031103787C00	3787	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3283MH0007630031103788C00	3788	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3283MH0007630031103789C00	3789	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3283MH0007630031103790C00	3790	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3283MH0007630031103791C00	3791	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3283MH0007630031103792C00	3792	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	85	6
3283MH0007630031103793C00	3793	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3283MH0007630031103794C00	3794	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3283 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Isle_of_Mists - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3283MH0007630011103796C00				
best focus image:	3283MH0001530001103832R00	3832	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3283MH0001530001103833S00	3833	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3283	focus merged on sol:		3283	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3283MH0007630031103798C00	3798	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3283MH0007630031103799C00	3799	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3283MH0007630031103800C00	3800	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3283MH0007630031103801C00	3801	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3283MH0007630031103802C00	3802	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3283MH0007630031103803C00	3803	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	85	6
3283MH0007630031103804C00	3804	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3283MH0007630031103805C00	3805	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3283 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Isle_of_Mists - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3283MH0007940011103807C00				
best focus image:	3283MH0001530001103830R00	3830	motor count:		15103	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3283MH0001530001103831S00	3831	acquired sequence:		mhli00794	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3283	focus merged on sol:		3283	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3283MH0007940031103809C00	3809	14911	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	255	1
3283MH0007940031103810C00	3810	14959	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	223	2
3283MH0007940031103811C00	3811	15007	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	191	3
3283MH0007940031103812C00	3812	15055	2.92	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	159	4
3283MH0007940031103813C00	3813	15103	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	127	5
3283MH0007940031103814C00	3814	15151	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	85	6
3283MH0007940031103815C00	3815	15199	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
3283MH0007940031103816C00	3816	15247	2.56	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3283 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Isle_of_Mists - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3283MH0007630011103818C00				
best focus image:	3283MH0001530001103828R00	3828	motor count:		13992	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3283MH0001530001103829S00	3829	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	31-Oct-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3283	focus merged on sol:		3283	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3283MH0007630031103820C00	3820	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3283MH0007630031103821C00	3821	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3283MH0007630031103822C00	3822	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3283MH0007630031103823C00	3823	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3283MH0007630031103824C00	3824	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3283MH0007630031103825C00	3825	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	85	6
3283MH0007630031103826C00	3826	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3283MH0007630031103827C00	3827	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3285 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3285MH0006990011103842C00			
best focus image:	3285MH0007030001103865R00		3865	motor count:		13929	range (cm):	7.3	
range map product:	3285MH0007030001103866S00		3866	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Nov-21			merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3285	focus merged on sol:		3285	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3285MH0006990031103844C00	3844	13809	8.29	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3285MH0006990031103845C00	3845	13839	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3285MH0006990031103846C00	3846	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	191	3
3285MH0006990031103847C00	3847	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
3285MH0006990031103848C00	3848	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	127	5
3285MH0006990031103849C00	3849	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	85	6
3285MH0006990031103850C00	3850	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	63	7
3285MH0006990031103851C00	3851	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3285 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3285MH0006990011103853C00			
best focus image:	3285MH0007030001103863R00		3863	motor count:		13928	range (cm):	7.3	
range map product:	3285MH0007030001103864S00		3864	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Nov-21			merge sequence:		mhli00703	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3285	focus merged on sol:		3285	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3285MH0006990031103855C00	3855	13808	8.30	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
3285MH0006990031103856C00	3856	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3285MH0006990031103857C00	3857	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	191	3
3285MH0006990031103858C00	3858	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
3285MH0006990031103859C00	3859	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	127	5
3285MH0006990031103860C00	3860	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	85	6
3285MH0006990031103861C00	3861	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	63	7
3285MH0006990031103862C00	3862	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

updated: 10_November_2021

Sol 3286 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3286MH0001820011103871C00			
best focus image:	3286MH0002650001103892R00		3892	motor count:		14021	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3286MH0002650001103893S00		3893	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3286	focus merged on sol:		3286	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3286MH0001820021103872C00	3872	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3286MH0001820021103873C00	3873	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3286MH0001820021103874C00	3874	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3286MH0001820021103875C00	3875	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3286MH0001820021103876C00	3876	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3286MH0001820021103877C00	3877	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	85	6
3286MH0001820021103878C00	3878	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3286MH0001820021103879C00	3879	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 10_November_2021

Sol 3286 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3286MH0001820011103881C00			
best focus image:	3286MH0002650001103890R00		3890	motor count:		14031	range (cm):	6.6	
range map product:	3286MH0002650001103891S00		3891	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	3-Nov-21			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3286	focus merged on sol:		3286	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3286MH0001820021103882C00	3882	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3286MH0001820021103883C00	3883	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3286MH0001820021103884C00	3884	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3286MH0001820021103885C00	3885	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
3286MH0001820021103886C00	3886	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3286MH0001820021103887C00	3887	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	85	6
3286MH0001820021103888C00	3888	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3286MH0001820021103889C00	3889	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_November_2021

Sol 3287 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Zechstein - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3287MH0007630011103898C00				
best focus image:	3287MH0001530001103949R00	3949	motor count:		14007	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3287MH0001530001103950S00	3950	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Nov-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3287	focus merged on sol:		3287	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3287MH0007630031103900C00	3900	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3287MH0007630031103901C00	3901	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3287MH0007630031103902C00	3902	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3287MH0007630031103903C00	3903	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3287MH0007630031103904C00	3904	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3287MH0007630031103905C00	3905	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	85	6
3287MH0007630031103906C00	3906	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3287MH0007630031103907C00	3907	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_November_2021

Sol 3287 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Zechstein - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3287MH0007630011103909C00				
best focus image:	3287MH0001530001103947R00	3947	motor count:		14012	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3287MH0001530001103948S00	3948	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Nov-21	merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3287	focus merged on sol:		3287	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3287MH0007630031103911C00	3911	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3287MH0007630031103912C00	3912	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3287MH0007630031103913C00	3913	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3287MH0007630031103914C00	3914	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3287MH0007630031103915C00	3915	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3287MH0007630031103916C00	3916	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	85	6
3287MH0007630031103917C00	3917	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3287MH0007630031103918C00	3918	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 08_November_2021

Sol 3287 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Zechstein - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3287MH0008010011103920C00				
best focus image:	3287MH0001530001103945R00	3945	motor count:		15145	range (cm):		2.7	
range map product:	3287MH0001530001103946S00	3946	acquired sequence:		mhli00801	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Nov-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3287	focus merged on sol:		3287	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3287MH0008010031103922C00	3922	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	255	1
3287MH0008010031103923C00	3923	15037	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3287MH0008010031103924C00	3924	15073	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3287MH0008010031103925C00	3925	15109	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
3287MH0008010031103926C00	3926	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3287MH0008010031103927C00	3927	15181	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	85	6
3287MH0008010031103928C00	3928	15217	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3287MH0008010031103929C00	3929	15253	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 08_November_2021

Sol 3287 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Zechstein - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3287MH0007630011103931C00				
best focus image:	3287MH0001530001103943R00	3943	motor count:		14016	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3287MH0001530001103944S00	3944	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Nov-21			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3287	focus merged on sol:		3287	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3287MH0007630031103933C00	3933	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3287MH0007630031103934C00	3934	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3287MH0007630031103935C00	3935	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3287MH0007630031103936C00	3936	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3287MH0007630031103937C00	3937	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3287MH0007630031103938C00	3938	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	85	6
3287MH0007630031103939C00	3939	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3287MH0007630031103940C00	3940	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI PI and his assistants draft each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 3193–3289. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 3194, 3195, 3197, 3199, 3201, 3202, 3203, 3204, 3205, 3206, 3208, 3209, 3210, 3211, 3212, 3214, 3215, 3216, 3217, 3219, 3221, 3222, 3224, 3229, 3245, 3246, 3247, 3272, 3273, 3274, 3276, 3277, 3278, 3279, 3280, 3283, 3284, 3285, 3286, 3287, 3289.**

updated: 03_August_2021

Sol 3194 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0_Aug_21
camera positions:	2
total parent images:	25
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	29

MAHLI imaged the target Bregout and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Bregout ~25 cm standoff	3194MH0001900001102655CDD	2655	autofocus sub-frame for target Bregout - standoff near 25 cm
		3194MH0001900001102656CDD	2656	target Bregout - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Bregout stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3194MH0001820001102667CDD	2657	autofocus sub-frame for target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3194MH0001820001102668CDD	2658	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3194MH0001820001102669CDD	2659	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102670CDD	2660	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102671CDD	2661	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102672CDD	2662	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102673CDD	2663	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102674CDD	2664	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102675CDD	2665	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102676CDD	2666	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Bregout stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3194MH0001820001102667CDD	2667	autofocus sub-frame for target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3194MH0001820001102668CDD	2668	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3194MH0001820001102669CDD	2669	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102670CDD	2670	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102671CDD	2671	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102672CDD	2672	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102673CDD	2673	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3194MH0001820001102674CDD	2674	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3194MH0002650001102677CDD	2677	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3194 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2669-2676 - best focus image product
		3194MH0002650001102678CDD	2678	target Bregout - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3194 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2669-2676 - range map product
		3194MH0002650001102679CDD	2679	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3194 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2659-2666 - best focus image product
		3194MH0002650001102680CDD	2680	target Bregout - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3194 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2659-2666 - range map product

updated: 02_August_2021

Sol 3195 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	@_img4100-4img
camera position	20
total parent images	20
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	20

image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID:	
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged 2 360° of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3195MH00769001102681E01	2681	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3195MH00770001102682E01	2682	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3195MH00771001102683E01	2683	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3195MH00772001102684E01	2684	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3195MH00769001102685E01	2685	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3195MH00770001102686E01	2686	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3195MH00771001102687E01	2687	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3195MH00772001102688E01	2688	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3195MH00769001102689E01	2689	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3195MH00770001102690E01	2690	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3195MH00771001102691E01	2691	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3195MH00772001102692E01	2692	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3195MH00769001102693E01	2693	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3195MH00770001102694E01	2694	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3195MH00771001102695E01	2695	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3195MH00772001102696E01	2696	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3195MH00769001102697E01	2697	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3195MH00770001102698E01	2698	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3195MH00771001102699E01	2699	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3195MH00772001102700E01	2700	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on Sol 3195 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm

updated: 06_August_2021

Sol 3197 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the target Vendore and the focus stack images were merged.													
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD												
		<table border="1"> <tr> <td>acquired/performed date(s)</td> <td>0-August-2021</td> </tr> <tr> <td>camera positions</td> <td>4</td> </tr> <tr> <td>total parent images</td> <td>33</td> </tr> <tr> <td>focus merges performed</td> <td>3</td> </tr> <tr> <td>total focus merge products</td> <td>6</td> </tr> <tr> <td>total parent images + focus merge products</td> <td>39</td> </tr> </table>		acquired/performed date(s)	0-August-2021	camera positions	4	total parent images	33	focus merges performed	3	total focus merge products	6	total parent images + focus merge products	39
acquired/performed date(s)	0-August-2021														
camera positions	4														
total parent images	33														
focus merges performed	3														
total focus merge products	6														
total parent images + focus merge products	39														
<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Image ID:</td> <td>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</td> </tr> <tr> <td>CPDPD:</td> <td>Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels</td> </tr> </table>				Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	CPDPD:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels								
Image ID:	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received														
CPDPD:	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels														
Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)															
mN00190	Vendore ~25 cm standoff	3197MH00190001102701C00	2701 autofocus sub-frame for target Vendore - standoff near 25 cm												
		3197MH00190001102702C00	2702 target Vendore - standoff near 25 cm												
		3197MH00299001102703C00	2703 autofocus sub-frame for target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm												
mN00299	Vendore stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3197MH00299001102704C00	2704 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm												
		3197MH00299001102705C00	2705 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102706C00	2706 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102707C00	2707 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102708C00	2708 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102709C00	2709 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102710C00	2710 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102711C00	2711 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH00299001102712C00	2712 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		mN00299	Vendore stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3197MH00299001102713C00	2713 autofocus sub-frame for target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm										
3197MH00299001102714C00	2714 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm														
3197MH00299001102715C00	2715 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102716C00	2716 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102717C00	2717 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102718C00	2718 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102719C00	2719 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102720C00	2720 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102721C00	2721 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack														
3197MH00299001102722C00	2722 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack														
mN00311	Vendore ~15 mm standoff	3197MH003110001102723C00	2723 autofocus sub-frame for target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm												
		3197MH003110001102724C00	2724 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm												
		3197MH003110001102725C00	2725 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102726C00	2726 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102727C00	2727 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102728C00	2728 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102729C00	2729 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102730C00	2730 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102731C00	2731 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack												
		3197MH003110001102732C00	2732 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack												
mN00299	Focus Merges	3197MH001930001102733R00	2733 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3197 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2725-2732 - best focus image product												
		3197MH001930001102734S00	2734 target Vendore - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3197 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2725-2732 - range map product												
		3197MH001930001102735R00	2735 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3197 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2715-2722 - best focus image product												
		3197MH001930001102736S00	2736 target Vendore - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3197 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2715-2722 - range map product												
		3197MH001930001102737R00	2737 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3197 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2705-2712 - best focus image product												
		3197MH001930001102738S00	2738 target Vendore - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3197 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2705-2712 - range map product												

Sol 3199 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6 Aug 21
camera positions	4
total parent images	51
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	59

MAHLI imaged the target Gabbliou and the ChemCam RWEB window and internal hardware. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Gabbliou ~25 cm standoff	3199MH0007060001102739C0D	2739	autofocus sub-frame for target Gabbliou - standoff near 25 cm
		3199MH000706001102740C0D	2740	target Gabbliou - standoff near 25 cm
		3199MH0007060021102741C0D	2741	target Gabbliou - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl000173	Gabbliou stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3199MH0001730001102742C0D	2742	autofocus sub-frame for target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3199MH000173001102743C0D	2743	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3199MH000173002102744C0D	2744	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173003102745C0D	2745	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173004102746C0D	2746	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173005102747C0D	2747	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173006102748C0D	2748	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173007102749C0D	2749	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173008102750C0D	2750	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173009102751C0D	2751	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl000173	Gabbliou stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3199MH0001730001102752C0D	2752	autofocus sub-frame for target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3199MH000173001102753C0D	2753	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3199MH000173002102754C0D	2754	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173003102755C0D	2755	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173004102756C0D	2756	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173005102757C0D	2757	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173006102758C0D	2758	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173007102759C0D	2759	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173008102760C0D	2760	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000173009102761C0D	2761	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl000520	ChemCam RWEB diagnostic imaging MAHLI at 45° angle to ChemCam ~25 cm standoff	3199MH000520001102762C0D	2762	autofocus sub-frame for ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm
		3199MH000520001102763C0D	2763	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm
		3199MH000520001102764C0D	2764	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102765C0D	2765	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102766C0D	2766	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102767C0D	2767	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102768C0D	2768	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102769C0D	2769	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102770C0D	2770	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102771C0D	2771	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102772C0D	2772	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 9 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102773C0D	2773	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 10 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102774C0D	2774	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 11 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102775C0D	2775	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 12 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102776C0D	2776	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 13 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102777C0D	2777	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 14 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102778C0D	2778	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 15 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102779C0D	2779	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 16 in 16-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520001102780C0D	2780	auto-exposure sub-frame for ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - focused manually on interior hardware for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm
		3199MH000520041102781C0D	2781	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - using exposure determined by preceding sub-frame - focused manually on interior hardware for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm
		3199MH000520005102782C0D	2782	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520005102783C0D	2783	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520005102784C0D	2784	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520005102785C0D	2785	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520005102786C0D	2786	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520005102787C0D	2787	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3199MH000520005102788C0D	2788	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3199MH000520005102789C0D	2789	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3199MH0006260001102790R0D	2790	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2782-2789 - best focus image product		
mhl000626	Focus Merges	3199MH0006260001102791S0D	2791	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2782-2789 - range map product
		3199MH0006260001102792R0D	2792	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2766-2773 - best focus image product
		3199MH0006260001102793S0D	2793	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2766-2773 - range map product
		3199MH0006260001102794R0D	2794	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2754-2761 - best focus image product
		3199MH0006260001102795S0D	2795	target Gabbliou - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2754-2761 - range map product
		3199MH0006260001102796R0D	2796	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2744-2751 - best focus image product
3199MH0006260001102797S0D	2797	target Gabbliou - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3199 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 2744-2751 - range map product		

updated: 12_August_2021

Sol 3201 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0 Aug 21
camera positions	12
total parent images	57
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	57

MAHLI imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets as well as the target Nadallac after DRT.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target ~5 cm working distance	3201MH0003710001102799C00	2798	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		3201MH0003710011102799C00	2799	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
mN000372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target ~5 cm working distance	3201MH0003720001102800C00	2800	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
		3201MH0003720011102800C00	2801	MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
mN000374	MAHLI cal target + wheel + surface ~30 cm working distance from target	3201MH0003740001102802C00	2802	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3201MH0003740011102803C00	2803	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target
		3201MH0003740021102804C00	2804	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity
mN000373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0003730001102805C00	2805	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0003730011102806C00	2806	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm
mN000390	Nadallac after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3201MH0001900001102807C00	2807	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3201MH0001900011102808C00	2808	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN000368	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo 1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0001680001102809C00	2809	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0001680011102810C00	2810	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0001680021102811C00	2811	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680031102812C00	2812	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680041102813C00	2813	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680051102814C00	2814	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680061102815C00	2815	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680071102816C00	2816	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680081102817C00	2817	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680091102818C00	2818	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000368	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo 2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0001680001102819C00	2819	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0001680011102820C00	2820	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0001680021102821C00	2821	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680031102822C00	2822	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680041102823C00	2823	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680051102824C00	2824	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680061102825C00	2825	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680071102826C00	2826	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680081102827C00	2827	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680091102828C00	2828	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000705	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0007050001102829C00	2829	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0007050011102830C00	2830	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN000705	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0007050001102831C00	2831	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0007050011102832C00	2832	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN000705	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0007050001102833C00	2833	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0007050011102834C00	2834	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN000743	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3201MH0007430001102835C00	2835	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3201MH0007430011102836C00	2836	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3201MH0007430021102837C00	2837	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430031102838C00	2838	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430041102839C00	2839	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430051102840C00	2840	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430061102841C00	2841	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430071102842C00	2842	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430081102843C00	2843	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0007430091102844C00	2844	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000368	Nadallac after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3201MH0001680001102845C00	2845	autofocus sub-frame for target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0001680011102846C00	2846	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3201MH0001680021102847C00	2847	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680031102848C00	2848	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680041102849C00	2849	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680051102850C00	2850	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680061102851C00	2851	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680071102852C00	2852	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680081102853C00	2853	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3201MH0001680091102854C00	2854	target Nadallac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 09_August_2021

Sol 3202 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Aug 21
camera positions:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3201 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3202MH00153000110285900	2855	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2847-2854 - best focus image product
		3202MH00153000110286000	2856	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2847-2854 - range map product
		3202MH00153000110286700	2857	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2837-2844 - best focus image product
		3202MH00153000110286800	2858	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2837-2844 - range map product
		3202MH00153000110286900	2859	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2821-2828 - best focus image product
		3202MH00153000110286000	2860	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2821-2828 - range map product
		3202MH00153000110286100	2861	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2811-2818 - best focus image product
		3202MH00153000110286200	2862	target Nadailiac - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3201 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2811-2818 - range map product

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3203 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	10-Aug-21	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Blis_et_Born after DRT and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00705	Blis_et_Born after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3203MH00070600011028630C0	2863	autofocus sub-frame for target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3203MH000706001102864C0	2864	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3203MH0007060021102865C0	2865	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
m1N00128	Blis_et_Born after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3203MH0001680001102866C0	2866	autofocus sub-frame for target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3203MH000168001102867C0	2867	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3203MH0001680021102868C0	2868	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680031102869C0	2869	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680041102870C0	2870	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680051102871C0	2871	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680061102872C0	2872	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680071102873C0	2873	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680081102874C0	2874	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680091102875C0	2875	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00128	Blis_et_Born after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3203MH0001680001102876C0	2876	autofocus sub-frame for target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3203MH000168001102877C0	2877	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3203MH0001680021102878C0	2878	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680031102879C0	2879	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680041102880C0	2880	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680051102881C0	2881	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680061102882C0	2882	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680071102883C0	2883	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680081102884C0	2884	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0001680091102885C0	2885	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00743	Blis_et_Born after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3203MH0007430001102886C0	2886	autofocus sub-frame for target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3203MH000743001102887C0	2887	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3203MH0007430021102888C0	2888	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430031102889C0	2889	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430041102890C0	2890	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430051102891C0	2891	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430061102892C0	2892	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430071102893C0	2893	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430081102894C0	2894	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3203MH0007430091102895C0	2895	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
m1N00193	Focus Merges	3203MH0001930001102896C0	2896	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3203 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2888-2895 - best focus image product
		3203MH000193001102897C0	2897	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3203 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2888-2895 - range map product
		3203MH0001930021102898C0	2898	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3203 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2878-2885 - best focus image product
		3203MH0001930031102899C0	2899	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3203 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2878-2885 - range map product
		3203MH0001930041102900C0	2900	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3203 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2868-2875 - best focus image product
3203MH0001930051102901C0	2901	target Blis_et_Born - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3203 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2868-2875 - range map product		

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3204 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-Aug-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Rodel and the REMS UV sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Rodel ~25 cm standoff	3204MH0007060001102902C00	2902	autofocus sub-frame for target Rodel - standoff near 25 cm
		3204MH0007060011102903C00	2903	target Rodel - standoff near 25 cm
		3204MH0007060021102904C00	2904	target Rodel - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00182	Rodel stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3204MH0001820001102905C00	2905	autofocus sub-frame for target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3204MH0001820011102906C00	2906	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3204MH0001820021102907C00	2907	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820031102908C00	2908	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820041102909C00	2909	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820051102910C00	2910	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820061102911C00	2911	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820071102912C00	2912	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820081102913C00	2913	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820091102914C00	2914	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Rodel stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3204MH0001820001102915C00	2915	autofocus sub-frame for target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3204MH0001820011102916C00	2916	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3204MH0001820021102917C00	2917	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820031102918C00	2918	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820041102919C00	2919	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820051102920C00	2920	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820061102921C00	2921	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820071102922C00	2922	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820081102923C00	2923	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3204MH0001820091102924C00	2924	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3204MH0000950001102925C00	2925	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3204MH000095001102926C00	2926	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00265	Focus Merges	3204MH0002650001102927R00	2927	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3204 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2917-2924 - best focus image product
		3204MH0002650001102928S00	2928	target Rodel - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3204 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2917-2924 - range map product
		3204MH0002650001102929R00	2929	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3204 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2907-2914 - best focus image product
		3204MH0002650001102930S00	2930	target Rodel - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3204 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2907-2914 - range map product

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3205 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12-Aug-21
camera position	7
total parent images	58
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	58

MAHLI imaged the targets Grishader and Barrackan.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00706	Grishader after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3205MH0007060001102933C00	2931	autofocus sub-frame for target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3205MH000706001102933C00	2932	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3205MH0007060021102933C00	2933	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00699	Grishader after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3205MH0006990001102934C00	2934	autofocus sub-frame for target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3205MH000699001102934C00	2935	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3205MH0006990021102934C00	2936	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3205MH0006990031102934C00	2937	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990041102934C00	2938	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990051102934C00	2939	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990061102940C00	2940	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990071102941C00	2941	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990081102942C00	2942	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990091102943C00	2943	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0006990101102944C00	2944	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00699	Grishader after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3205MH0006990001102945C00	2945	autofocus sub-frame for target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3205MH000699001102946C00	2946			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
3205MH0006990021102947C00	2947			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3205MH0006990031102948C00	2948			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990041102949C00	2949			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990051102950C00	2950			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990061102951C00	2951			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990071102952C00	2952			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990081102953C00	2953			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990091102954C00	2954			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0006990101102955C00	2955			target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00732	Grishader after DRT ~2 cm standoff			3205MH0007320001102956C00	2956	autofocus sub-frame for target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3205MH000732001102957C00	2957	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm		
		3205MH0007320021102958C00	2958	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3205MH0007320031102959C00	2959	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320041102960C00	2960	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320051102961C00	2961	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320061102962C00	2962	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320071102963C00	2963	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320081102964C00	2964	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320091102965C00	2965	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0007320101102966C00	2966	target Grishader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00190	Barrackan ~25 cm standoff	3205MH0001900001102967C00	2967	autofocus sub-frame for target Barrackan - standoff near 25 cm
3205MH000190001102968C00	2968			target Barrackan - standoff near 25 cm		
mNI00152	Barrackan stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3205MH000152001102969C00	2969	autofocus sub-frame for target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3205MH0001520021102970C00	2970	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3205MH0001520031102971C00	2971	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520041102972C00	2972	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520051102973C00	2973	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520061102974C00	2974	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520071102975C00	2975	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520081102976C00	2976	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520091102977C00	2977	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3205MH0001520101102978C00	2978	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00152	Barrackan stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3205MH000152001102979C00	2979	autofocus sub-frame for target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3205MH0001520021102980C00	2980	target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
3205MH0001520031102981C00	2981			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520041102982C00	2982			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520051102983C00	2983			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520061102984C00	2984			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520071102985C00	2985			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520081102986C00	2986			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520091102987C00	2987			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3205MH0001520101102988C00	2988			target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 13_August_2021

Sol 3206 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-Aug-21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3205 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3206MH000227000110298900	2989	target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2981-2988 - best focus image product
		3206MH000227000110299050	2990	target Barrackan - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2981-2988 - range map product
		3206MH000227000110299100	2991	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2971-2978 - best focus image product
		3206MH000227000110299250	2992	target Barrackan - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2971-2978 - range map product
		3206MH000227000110299300	2993	target Grimshader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2955-2966 - best focus image product
		3206MH000227000110299450	2994	target Grimshader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2955-2966 - range map product
		3206MH000227000110299500	2995	target Grimshader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2948-2955 - best focus image product
		3206MH000227000110299650	2996	target Grimshader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2948-2955 - range map product
		3206MH000227000110299700	2997	target Grimshader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2937-2944 - best focus image product
		3206MH000227000110299850	2998	target Grimshader - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3205 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2937-2944 - range map product

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3208 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	15-Aug-21	
		camera positions:	49	Image ID:
		total parent images:	49	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products:	49	
summary of MAHLI activities				
During the day, MAHLI imaged the targets Inaccessible_Pinnacle and KilmaLuag. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Inaccessible_Pinnacle ~23 cm standoff	3208MH0001900001102999C00	2999	autofocus sub-frame for target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - standoff near 23 cm
		3208MH0001900011103000C00	3000	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - standoff near 23 cm
mN002197	Inaccessible_Pinnacle stereo 1 ~35 mm standoff	3208MH0002970001103001C00	3001	autofocus sub-frame for target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970011103002C00	3002	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970021103003C00	3003	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970031103004C00	3004	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970041103005C00	3005	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970051103006C00	3006	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970061103007C00	3007	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970071103008C00	3008	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970081103009C00	3009	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970091103010C00	3010	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002197	Inaccessible_Pinnacle stereo 2 ~35 mm standoff	3208MH0002970001103011C00	3011	autofocus sub-frame for target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970011103012C00	3012	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970021103013C00	3013	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970031103014C00	3014	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970041103015C00	3015	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970051103016C00	3016	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970061103017C00	3017	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970071103018C00	3018	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970081103019C00	3019	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970091103020C00	3020	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002190	KilmaLuag ~25 cm standoff	3208MH0001900001103021C00	3021	autofocus sub-frame for target KilmaLuag - standoff near 25 cm
		3208MH0001900011103022C00	3022	target KilmaLuag - standoff near 25 cm
mN002197	KilmaLuag stereo 1 ~35 mm standoff	3208MH0002970001103023C00	3023	autofocus sub-frame for target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970011103024C00	3024	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970021103025C00	3025	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970031103026C00	3026	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970041103027C00	3027	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970051103028C00	3028	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970061103029C00	3029	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970071103030C00	3030	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970081103031C00	3031	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970091103032C00	3032	target KilmaLuag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002197	KilmaLuag stereo 2 ~35 mm standoff	3208MH0002970001103033C00	3033	autofocus sub-frame for target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970011103034C00	3034	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3208MH0002970021103035C00	3035	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970031103036C00	3036	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970041103037C00	3037	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970051103038C00	3038	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970061103039C00	3039	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970071103040C00	3040	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970081103041C00	3041	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3208MH0002970091103042C00	3042	target KilmaLuag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN003212	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover opens position 1 of 3; imaging at right	3208MH0003120001103043C00	3043	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
		3208MH0003120011103044C00	3044	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN003216	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3208MH0003160001103045C00	3045	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN003216	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3208MH0003160001103046C00	3046	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN003218	~17 cm above open CheMin inlet	3208MH0003180001103047C00	3047	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 17 cm working distance

updated: 16_August_2021

Sol 3209 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Aug-21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI images that correspond to CDPIDs 3927 through 4840 (data from Sols 2935-2993) were deleted from the MAHLI DEA non-volatile memory storage. The focus stack images from Sol 3208 were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3209MH001530001103048R00	3048	target Kilimaluag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3035-3042 - best focus image product
		3209MH001530001103049S00	3049	target Kilimaluag - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3035-3042 - range map product
		3209MH001530001103050R00	3050	target Kilimaluag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3025-3032 - best focus image product
		3209MH001530001103051S00	3051	target Kilimaluag - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3025-3032 - range map product
		3209MH001530001103052R00	3052	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3013-3020 - best focus image product
		3209MH001530001103053S00	3053	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3013-3020 - range map product
		3209MH001530001103054R00	3054	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3003-3010 - best focus image product
		3209MH001530001103055S00	3055	target Inaccessible_Pinnacle - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3208 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3003-3010 - range map product

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3210 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Aug-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Solway_Lowlands after DRT and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Solway_Lowlands after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3210MH001900001103056C00	3056	autofocus sub-frame for target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3210MH00190001103057C00	3057	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Solway_Lowlands after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3210MH001680001103058C00	3058	autofocus sub-frame for target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3210MH00168001103059C00	3059	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3210MH001680021103060C00	3060	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680031103061C00	3061	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680041103062C00	3062	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680051103063C00	3063	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680061103064C00	3064	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680071103065C00	3065	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680081103066C00	3066	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680091103067C00	3067	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Solway_Lowlands after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3210MH001680001103068C00	3068	autofocus sub-frame for target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3210MH00168001103069C00	3069	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3210MH001680021103070C00	3070	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680031103071C00	3071	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680041103072C00	3072	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680051103073C00	3073	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680061103074C00	3074	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680071103075C00	3075	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680081103076C00	3076	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH001680091103077C00	3077	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Solway_Lowlands after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3210MH003020001103078C00	3078	autofocus sub-frame for target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3210MH00302001103079C00	3079	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3210MH003020021103080C00	3080	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020031103081C00	3081	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020041103082C00	3082	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020051103083C00	3083	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020061103084C00	3084	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020071103085C00	3085	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020081103086C00	3086	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3210MH003020091103087C00	3087	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3210MH001930001103088R00	3088	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3210 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3080-3087 - best focus image product
		3210MH001930001103089S00	3089	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3210 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3080-3087 - range map product
		3210MH001930001103090R00	3090	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3210 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3070-3077 - best focus image product
		3210MH001930001103091S00	3091	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3210 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3070-3077 - range map product
		3210MH001930001103092R00	3092	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3210 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3060-3067 - best focus image product
3210MH001930001103093S00	3093	target Solway_Lowlands - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3210 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3060-3067 - range map product		

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3212 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19-Aug-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	32
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	38

MAHLI imaged the target Camster_Cairns and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Camster_Cairns ~25 cm standoff	3120	3120	autofocus sub-frame for target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 25 cm
		3121	3121	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Camster_Cairns stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3122	3122	autofocus sub-frame for target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3123	3123	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3124	3124	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3125	3125	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3126	3126	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3127	3127	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3128	3128	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3129	3129	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3130	3130	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3131	3131	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Camster_Cairns stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3132	3132	autofocus sub-frame for target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3133	3133	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3134	3134	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3135	3135	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3136	3136	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3137	3137	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3138	3138	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3139	3139	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3140	3140	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3141	3141	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Camster_Cairns ~1 cm standoff	3142	3142	autofocus sub-frame for target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm
		3143	3143	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm
		3144	3144	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3145	3145	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3146	3146	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3147	3147	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3148	3148	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3149	3149	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3150	3150	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3151	3151	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3152	3152	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3212 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3144-3151 - best focus image product
		3153	3153	target Camster_Cairns - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3212 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3144-3151 - range map product
		3154	3154	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3212 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3134-3141 - best focus image product
		3155	3155	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3212 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3134-3141 - range map product
		3156	3156	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3212 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3124-3131 - best focus image product
		3157	3157	target Camster_Cairns - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3212 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3124-3131 - range map product

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3214 - MAHI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Aug-21
camera position	0
total parent images	48
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	48

Image ID:
 black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHI activities

MAHI imaged the target Newcraigall after DRT.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Newcraigall after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3214MH0019000011031580C0	3158	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3214MH00190001103159C0	3159	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Newcraigall after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3214MH001680001103160C0	3160	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH00168001103161C0	3161	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH001680021103162C0	3162	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680031103163C0	3163	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680041103164C0	3164	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680051103165C0	3165	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680061103166C0	3166	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680071103167C0	3167	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680081103168C0	3168	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680091103169C0	3169	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Newcraigall after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3214MH001680001103170C0	3170	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH00168001103171C0	3171	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH001680021103172C0	3172	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680031103173C0	3173	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680041103174C0	3174	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680051103175C0	3175	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680061103176C0	3176	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680071103177C0	3177	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680081103178C0	3178	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680091103179C0	3179	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Newcraigall after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3214MH007050001103180C0	3180	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH00705001103181C0	3181	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Newcraigall after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3214MH007050001103182C0	3182	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH00705001103183C0	3183	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Newcraigall after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3214MH007050001103184C0	3184	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH00705001103185C0	3185	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00743	Newcraigall after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3214MH007430001103186C0	3186	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3214MH00743001103187C0	3187	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3214MH007430021103188C0	3188	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430031103189C0	3189	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430041103190C0	3190	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430051103191C0	3191	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430061103192C0	3192	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430071103193C0	3193	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430081103194C0	3194	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH007430091103195C0	3195	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Newcraigall after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3214MH001680001103196C0	3196	autofocus sub-frame for target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH00168001103197C0	3197	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3214MH001680021103198C0	3198	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680031103199C0	3199	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680041103200C0	3200	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680051103201C0	3201	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680061103202C0	3202	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680071103203C0	3203	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680081103204C0	3204	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3214MH001680091103205C0	3205	target Newcraigall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 27_August_2021

Sol 3215 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		22-Aug-21		
Camera position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image ID	
total parent images	27		black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received	
total focus merge products	0		CPDPD	
total parent images + focus merge products	27		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
summary of MAHLI activities: The ChemCam RWB, Mazcams, and Navcams, on the Remote Sensing Mast (RSM) with the Marsky and landscape in the background. A day time image was acquired to show the context. This imaging was repeated at night. In total, the right imaging included dark current images (dust cover closed, focus at motor count 0), three images of Phobos in the sky, and 17 images of the RSM hardware and landscape.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00830	Phobos shine experiment RSM - daylight context	3215MH000830001103206C00	3206	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - daylight context image - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff
mN00831	Phobos shine experiment dark current dust cover closed no focus mechanism motion	3215MH000831001103207C00	3207	Phobos shine experiment - dark current image - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure
mN00832	Phobos	3215MH000832001103208C00	3208	Phobos shine experiment - dark current image - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure
		3215MH000832001103209C00	3209	Phobos shine experiment - Phobos near azimuth 277-degrees elevation 35-degrees in the night sky - no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity
		3215MH000832001103210C00	3210	Phobos shine experiment - Phobos near azimuth 277-degrees elevation 35-degrees in the night sky - no LEDs on - 500 millisecond manual exposure - manual focus at infinity
mN00831	Phobos shine experiment dark current dust cover closed no focus mechanism motion	3215MH000831001103211C00	3211	Phobos shine experiment - Phobos near azimuth 277-degrees elevation 35-degrees in the night sky - no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus at infinity
		3215MH000831001103212C00	3212	Phobos shine experiment - dark current image - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure
mN00832	Phobos shine experiment RSM - night imaging	3215MH000832001103213C00	3213	Phobos shine experiment - dark current image - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure
		3215MH000832001103214C00	3214	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 1 of 17
		3215MH000832001103215C00	3215	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 2 of 17
		3215MH000832001103216C00	3216	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 3 of 17
		3215MH000832001103217C00	3217	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 4 of 17
		3215MH000832001103218C00	3218	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 5 of 17
		3215MH000832001103219C00	3219	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 6 of 17
		3215MH000832001103220C00	3220	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 7 of 17
		3215MH000832001103221C00	3221	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 8 of 17
		3215MH000832001103222C00	3222	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 9 of 17
		3215MH000832001103223C00	3223	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 10 of 17
		3215MH000832001103224C00	3224	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 11 of 17
		3215MH000832001103225C00	3225	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 12 of 17
		3215MH000832001103226C00	3226	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 13 of 17
		3215MH000832001103227C00	3227	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 14 of 17
		3215MH000832001103228C00	3228	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 15 of 17
		3215MH000832001103229C00	3229	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 16 of 17
3215MH000832001103230C00	3230	Phobos shine experiment - cover remote sensing mast (RSM) - night image with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure - manual focus assumes -3 meter standoff - image 17 of 17		
mN00831	Phobos shine experiment dark current dust cover closed no focus mechanism motion	3215MH000831001103231C00	3231	Phobos shine experiment - dark current image - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure
		3215MH000831001103232C00	3232	Phobos shine experiment - dark current image - no focus mechanism motion - dust cover closed - at night with no LEDs on - 60 second manual exposure

updated: 23_August_2021

Sol 3216 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	23-Aug-21
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3214 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3216MH00153000110323900	3233	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3198-3205 - best focus image product
		3216MH001530001103234500	3234	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3198-3205 - range map product
		3216MH001530001103235900	3235	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3188-3195 - best focus image product
		3216MH001530001103236500	3236	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3188-3195 - range map product
		3216MH001530001103237900	3237	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3172-3179 - best focus image product
		3216MH001530001103238500	3238	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3172-3179 - range map product
		3216MH001530001103239900	3239	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3162-3169 - best focus image product
		3216MH001530001103240500	3240	target Newcraighall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3214 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3162-3169 - range map product

updated: 07_September_2021

Sol 3217 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Aug-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	26

MAHLI imaged the target Spiggle and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Spiggle ~25 cm standoff	3217MH0001900001103241C0D	3241	autofocus sub-frame for target Spiggle - standoff near 25 cm
		3217MH0001900001103242C0D	3242	target Spiggle - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Spiggle stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3217MH0001820001103243C0D	3243	autofocus sub-frame for target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3217MH0001820001103244C0D	3244	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3217MH0001820001103245C0D	3245	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103246C0D	3246	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103247C0D	3247	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103248C0D	3248	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103249C0D	3249	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103250C0D	3250	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103251C0D	3251	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103252C0D	3252	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Spiggle stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3217MH0001820001103253C0D	3253	autofocus sub-frame for target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3217MH0001820001103254C0D	3254	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3217MH0001820001103255C0D	3255	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103256C0D	3256	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103257C0D	3257	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103258C0D	3258	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103259C0D	3259	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103260C0D	3260	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103261C0D	3261	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3217MH0001820001103262C0D	3262	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	3217MH0002050001103263R0D	3263	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3217 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3255-3262 - best focus image product
		3217MH0002050001103264S0D	3264	target Spiggle - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3217 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3255-3262 - range map product
		3217MH0002050001103265R0D	3265	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3217 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3245-3252 - best focus image product
		3217MH0002050001103266S0D	3266	target Spiggle - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3217 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3245-3252 - range map product

updated: 31_August_2021

Sol 3219 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Aug-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	32
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	38

MAHLI imaged the target Smallholms and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Smallholm ~25 cm standoff	3219MH0001900011032670CD	3267	autofocus sub-frame for target Smallholm - standoff near 25 cm
		3219MH0001900011032680CD	3268	target Smallholm - standoff near 25 cm
mN002152	Smallholm stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3219MH0001520011032690CD	3269	autofocus sub-frame for target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3219MH0001520011032700CD	3270	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3219MH0001520011032710CD	3271	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032720CD	3272	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032730CD	3273	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032740CD	3274	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032750CD	3275	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032760CD	3276	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032770CD	3277	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032780CD	3278	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002152	Smallholm stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3219MH0001520011032790CD	3279	autofocus sub-frame for target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3219MH0001520011032800CD	3280	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3219MH0001520011032810CD	3281	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032820CD	3282	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032830CD	3283	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032840CD	3284	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032850CD	3285	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032860CD	3286	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032870CD	3287	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0001520011032880CD	3288	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	Smallholm ~6 mm standoff	3219MH0007430011032890CD	3289	autofocus sub-frame for target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm
		3219MH0007430011032900CD	3290	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm
		3219MH0007430011032910CD	3291	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032920CD	3292	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032930CD	3293	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032940CD	3294	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032950CD	3295	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032960CD	3296	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032970CD	3297	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3219MH0007430011032980CD	3298	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	3219MH0001930011032990CD	3299	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3219 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3291-3298 - best focus image product
		3219MH0001930011033000CD	3300	target Smallholm - standoff near 6 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3219 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3291-3298 - range map product
		3219MH0001930011033010CD	3301	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3219 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3281-3288 - best focus image product
		3219MH0001930011033020CD	3302	target Smallholm - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3219 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3281-3288 - range map product
		3219MH0001930011033030CD	3303	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3219 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3271-3278 - best focus image product
3219MH0001930011033040CD	3304	target Smallholm - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3219 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3271-3278 - range map product		

updated: 31_August_2021

SOL 3221 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)		28-Aug-21			
		camera positions	55	Image ID:			
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received			
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:			
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels			
		total parent images + focus merge products	55				
summary of MAHLI activities							
During the day, MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Saltopus. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.							
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)			
mNI00190	Saltopus before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3221MH0001900001103305CD	3305	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm			
		3221MH0001900011103306CD	3306	target Saltopus - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm			
mNI00122	Saltopus before DRT ~5 cm standoff	3221MH0001220001103307CD	3307	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm			
		3221MH0001220011103308CD	3308	target Saltopus - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm			
mNI00706	Saltopus after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3221MH0007060001103309CD	3309	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm			
		3221MH0007060011103310CD	3310	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm			
mNI00834	Saltopus after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3221MH0008340001103311CD	3311	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
		3221MH0008340001103312CD	3312	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm			
		3221MH0008340011103313CD	3313	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm			
		3221MH0008340011103314CD	3314	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
		3221MH0008340011103315CD	3315	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103316CD	3316	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103317CD	3317	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103318CD	3318	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103319CD	3319	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103320CD	3320	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103321CD	3321	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008340011103322CD	3322	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mNI00834	Saltopus after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3221MH0008340011103323CD	3323	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
				3221MH0008340011103324CD	3324	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm	
3221MH0008340011103325CD	3325			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure			
3221MH0008340011103326CD	3326			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103327CD	3327			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103328CD	3328			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103329CD	3329			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103330CD	3330			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103331CD	3331			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103332CD	3332			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103333CD	3333			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
mNI00835	Saltopus after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff			3221MH0008350001103334CD	3334	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm	
				3221MH0008350011103335CD	3335	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm	
				3221MH0008350011103336CD	3336	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
		3221MH0008350011103337CD	3337	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103338CD	3338	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103339CD	3339	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103340CD	3340	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103341CD	3341	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103342CD	3342	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103343CD	3343	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		3221MH0008350011103344CD	3344	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack			
		mNI00834	Saltopus after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3221MH0008340001103345CD	3345	autofocus sub-frame for target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm	
				3221MH0008340011103346CD	3346	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm	
				3221MH0008340011103347CD	3347	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
3221MH0008340011103348CD	3348			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103349CD	3349			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103350CD	3350			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103351CD	3351			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103352CD	3352			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103353CD	3353			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack			
3221MH0008340011103354CD	3354			target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack			
mNI00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh, inlet cover open; position 1 of 3, imaging at right	3221MH0003120001103356CD	3356	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance			
		3221MH0003120011103357CD	3357	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance			
mNI00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3221MH0003260001103358CD	3358	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance			
mNI00326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3221MH0003260001103359CD	3359	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance			
mNI00228	~17 cm above open CheMin inlet	3221MH0002280001103360CD	3360	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 17 cm working distance			

updated: 30_August_2021

Sol 3222 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29-Aug-21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3221 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3222MH001530001103261900	3361	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3348-3355 - best focus image product
		3222MH001530001103362500	3362	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3348-3355 - range map product
		3222MH001530001103263900	3363	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3327-3344 - best focus image product
		3222MH001530001103364500	3364	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3337-3344 - range map product
		3222MH001530001103265900	3365	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3326-3333 - best focus image product
		3222MH001530001103366500	3366	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3326-3333 - range map product
		3222MH001530001103267900	3367	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3315-3322 - best focus image product
		3222MH001530001103368500	3368	target Saltopus - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3221 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3315-3322 - range map product

updated: 01_September_2021

Sol 3224 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	# images/stacks			
		camera position	6	image ID		
		total parent images	49	black - best, best-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID		
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	57			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Maria_Gordon after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mhl00706	Maria_Gordon after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3224MH000706000110289000	3369	autofocus sub-frame for intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3224MH000706001103370000	3370	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3224MH00070600211029710000	3371	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3224MH000834001103372000	3372	autofocus sub-frame for intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
mhl00834	Maria_Gordon after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3224MH000834001103373000	3373	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3224MH0008340021103374000	3374	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3224MH0008340031103375000	3375	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008340041103376000	3376	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008340051103377000	3377	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008340061103378000	3378	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008340071103379000	3379	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008340081103380000	3380	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH00083400911033810000	3381	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH00083401011033820000	3382	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00834	Maria_Gordon after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3224MH000834001103383000	3383	autofocus sub-frame for intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3224MH0008340021103384000	3384	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3224MH0008340031103385000	3385			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3224MH0008340041103386000	3386			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH0008340051103387000	3387			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH0008340061103388000	3388			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH0008340071103389000	3389			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH0008340081103390000	3390			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083400911033910000	3391			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083401011033920000	3392			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH0008340111033930000	3393			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mhl00835	Maria_Gordon after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff			3224MH000835001103394000	3394	autofocus sub-frame for intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3224MH0008350021103395000	3395	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm		
		3224MH0008350031103396000	3396	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3224MH0008350041103397000	3397	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008350051103398000	3398	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008350061103399000	3399	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008350071103400000	3400	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH00083500811034010000	3401	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH00083500911034020000	3402	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH00083501011034030000	3403	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3224MH0008350111034040000	3404	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mhl00834	Maria_Gordon after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3224MH000834001103405000	3405	autofocus sub-frame for intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
3224MH0008340021103406000	3406			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
3224MH00083400311034070000	3407			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3224MH00083400411034080000	3408			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083400511034090000	3409			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083400611034100000	3410			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083400711034110000	3411			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083400811034120000	3412			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083400911034130000	3413			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH00083401011034140000	3414			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3224MH0008340111034150000	3415			intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mhl00465	Maria_Gordon after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff			3224MH000465001103416000	3416	autofocus sub-frame for intended Maria_Gordon drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3224 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3224MH00046500211034170000	3417	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3224 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm		
mhl00153	Focus Merges	3224MH001530001103418000	3418	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3408-3415 - best focus image product		
		3224MH0015300021103419000	3419	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3408-3415 - range map product		
		3224MH0015300031103420000	3420	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3397-3404 - best focus image product		
		3224MH00153000411034210000	3421	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3397-3404 - range map product		
		3224MH00153000511034220000	3422	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3386-3393 - best focus image product		
		3224MH00153000611034230000	3423	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3386-3393 - range map product		
		3224MH00153000711034240000	3424	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3375-3382 - best focus image product		
3224MH00153000811034250000	3425	intended Maria_Gordon drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3224 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3375-3382 - range map product				

updated: 23_September_2021

Sol 3245 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Sep-21
camera positions	6
total parent images	13
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	13

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Maria_Gordon sample discard pile, the surfaces surrounding SAM Inlet #2, with the inlet cover open, a follow-up to Maria_Gordon sample drop-offs and the Maria_Gordon drill hole.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile ~25 cm standoff	3245MH001970001103432C00	3432	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3245MH001970011103433C00	3433	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3245MH001220001103434C00	3434	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3245MH001220011103435C00	3435	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00122	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~45 mm standoff	3245MH001220001103436C00	3436	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3245MH001220011103437C00	3437	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm
mN00779	SAM Inlet 2 ~20 cm standoff	3245MH00779001103438C00	3438	SAM Inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - manual focus assuming 231 mm working distance
		3245MH00779001103439C00	3439	autofocus sub-frame for SAM Inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
		3245MH00779001103440C00	3440	SAM Inlet 2 cover open after sample drop-off - inspect surface surrounding inlet perimeter - standoff near 20 cm
mN00197	Maria_Gordon drill hole drilled on Sol 3229 ~25 cm standoff	3245MH001970001103441C00	3441	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Maria_Gordon - drilled sol 3229 - standoff near 25 cm
		3245MH00197001103442C00	3442	drill hole in rock named Maria_Gordon - drilled sol 3229 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00774	Maria_Gordon drill hole drilled on Sol 3229 ~10 cm standoff	3245MH00774001103443C00	3443	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Maria_Gordon - drilled sol 3229 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 10 cm
		3245MH00774001103444C00	3444	drill hole in rock named Maria_Gordon - drilled sol 3229 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 10 cm

updated: 24_September_2021

Sol 3246 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	23-Sep-21			
		camera positions	2	Image ID:		
		total parent images	27	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	1	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	2	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	29			
summary of MAHLI activities: During the day, MAHLI imaged the Maria_Gordon Sample Discard Pile. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the ChemIn inlet for cleanliness and MAHLI also imaged the Maria_Gordon drill hole wall that was investigated by ChemCam. Focus stack images were also merged.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00122	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile APXS spot 1 ~55 mm standoff	3246MH000122001103445C00	3245	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3246MH000122001103446C00	3246	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm		
mN00122	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile APXS spot 2 ~55 mm standoff	3246MH000122001103447C00	3247	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3246MH000122001103448C00	3248	Maria_Gordon sample discard pile - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 55 mm		
mN00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above ChemIn inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	3246MH000312001103449C00	3249	ChemIn sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance		
		3246MH000312001103450C00	3250	ChemIn sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance		
mN00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3246MH000312001103451C00	3251	ChemIn sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance		
mN00326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3246MH000312001103452C00	3252	ChemIn sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance		
mN00328	~17 cm above open ChemIn inlet	3246MH0002180001103453C00	3253	ChemIn sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 17 cm working distance		
mN00410	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall MAHLI pointing southwest 30" from normal right imaging ~7 cm standoff	3246MH000410001103454C00	3254	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on		
		3246MH000410001103455C00	3255	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on		
		3246MH000410001103456C00	3256	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 1 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103457C00	3257	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 2 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103458C00	3258	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 3 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103459C00	3259	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 4 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103460C00	3260	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 5 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103461C00	3261	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 6 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103462C00	3262	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 7 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103463C00	3263	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 8 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103464C00	3264	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 9 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103465C00	3265	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 10 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103466C00	3266	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 11 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103467C00	3267	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 12 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103468C00	3268	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 13 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103469C00	3269	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 14 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103470C00	3270	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 15 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		3246MH000410001103471C00	3271	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - image 16 in 16-image absolute focus stack		
		mN00470	Focus Merge	3246MH000470001103472C00	3272	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 3246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID 3246-3247 - best focus image product
				3246MH000470001103473C00	3273	Maria_Gordon drill hole wall - MAHLI pointing southwest - 30 degrees from normal and 7 cm standoff from plane defined by top of hole - night imaging - all white LEDs on - focus stack acquired sol 3246 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID 3246-3247 - range map product

updated: 29_September_2021

Sol 3247 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Sep-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	2
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	2

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Maria_Gordon Drill Cuttings.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00122	Maria_Gordon drill cuttings ~5 cm standoff	3247MH001220001103474C00	3274	autofocus sub-frame for Maria_Gordon drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
		3247MH0001220011103475C00	3275	Maria_Gordon drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm

Sol 3272 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	20-Oct-21	
		camera positions	83	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	83	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Goose_Stone and Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN100706	Goose_Stone ~25 cm standoff	3272MH0007060001103476C0D	3476	autofocus sub-frame for target Goose_Stone - standoff near 25 cm
		3272MH000706001103477C0D	3477	target Goose_Stone - standoff near 25 cm
		3272MH0007060021103478C0D	3478	target Goose_Stone - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100740	Goose_Stone stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3272MH0007400001103479C0D	3479	autofocus sub-frame for target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3272MH000740001103480C0D	3480	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3272MH0007400021103481C0D	3481	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007400031103482C0D	3482	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400041103483C0D	3483	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400051103484C0D	3484	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400061103485C0D	3485	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400071103486C0D	3486	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400081103487C0D	3487	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400091103488C0D	3488	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400101103489C0D	3489	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100740	Goose_Stone stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3272MH000740001103490C0D	3490	autofocus sub-frame for target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3272MH0007400021103491C0D	3491	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3272MH0007400031103492C0D	3492	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007400041103493C0D	3493	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400051103494C0D	3494	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400061103495C0D	3495	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400071103496C0D	3496	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400081103497C0D	3497	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400091103498C0D	3498	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007400101103499C0D	3499	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH000740011103500C0D	3500	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100706	Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds ~25 cm standoff	3272MH000706001103501C0D	3501	autofocus sub-frame for target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3272MH0007060021103502C0D	3502	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3272MH0007060031103503C0D	3503	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100714	Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds APXS spot 1 ~4 cm standoff	3272MH000714001103504C0D	3504	autofocus sub-frame for target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3272MH0007140021103505C0D	3505	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3272MH0007140031103506C0D	3506	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007140041103507C0D	3507	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140051103508C0D	3508	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140061103509C0D	3509	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140071103510C0D	3510	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140081103511C0D	3511	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140091103512C0D	3512	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140101103513C0D	3513	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH000714011103514C0D	3514	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100714	Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds APXS spot 2 ~45 mm standoff	3272MH000714001103515C0D	3515	autofocus sub-frame for target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3272MH0007140021103516C0D	3516	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3272MH0007140031103517C0D	3517	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007140041103518C0D	3518	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140051103519C0D	3519	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140061103520C0D	3520	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140071103521C0D	3521	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140081103522C0D	3522	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140091103523C0D	3523	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140101103524C0D	3524	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH000714011103525C0D	3525	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN100714	Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds APXS spot 3 ~45 mm standoff	3272MH000714001103526C0D	3526	autofocus sub-frame for target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm
		3272MH0007140021103527C0D	3527	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm
		3272MH0007140031103528C0D	3528	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007140041103529C0D	3529	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140051103530C0D	3530	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140061103531C0D	3531	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140071103532C0D	3532	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140081103533C0D	3533	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140091103534C0D	3534	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140101103535C0D	3535	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH000714011103536C0D	3536	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mNH00714	Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds APXS spot 4 ~6 cm standoff	3272MH0007140001103537C00	3537	autofocus sub-frame for target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm
		3272MH0007140011103538C00	3538	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm
		3272MH0007140021103539C00	3539	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007140031103540C00	3540	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140041103541C00	3541	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140051103542C00	3542	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140061103543C00	3543	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140071103544C00	3544	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140081103545C00	3545	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140091103546C00	3546	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3272MH0007140101103547C00	3547	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNH00714	Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds APXS spot 5 ~5 cm standoff	3272MH0007140001103548C00	3548	autofocus sub-frame for target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3272MH0007140011103549C00	3549	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3272MH0007140021103550C00	3550	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3272MH0007140031103551C00	3551	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140041103552C00	3552	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140051103553C00	3553	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140061103554C00	3554	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140071103555C00	3555	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140081103556C00	3556	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3272MH0007140091103557C00	3557	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3272MH0007140101103558C00	3558	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 21_October_2021

Sol 3273 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-Oct-21
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3272 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000171	Focus Merges	3273MH000171000110359900	3559	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3551-3558 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110356000	3560	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 5 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3551-3558 - range map product
		3273MH000171000110356100	3561	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3540-3547 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110356200	3562	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 4 - standoff near 6 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3540-3547 - range map product
		3273MH000171000110356300	3563	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3529-3536 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110356400	3564	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3529-3536 - range map product
		3273MH000171000110356900	3565	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3518-3525 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110356600	3566	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3518-3525 - range map product
		3273MH000171000110356700	3567	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3507-3514 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110356800	3568	target Helmsdale_Boulder_Beds - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3507-3514 - range map product
		3273MH000171000110356900	3569	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3493-3500 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110357000	3570	target Goose_Stone - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3493-3500 - range map product
		3273MH000171000110357100	3571	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3482-3489 - best focus image product
		3273MH000171000110357200	3572	target Goose_Stone - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3272 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3482-3489 - range map product

updated: 25_October_2021

Sol 3274 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Oct-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the target Acadian and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Acadian ~25 cm standoff	3274MH000706001103575000	3573	autofocus sub-frame for target Acadian - standoff near 25 cm
		3274MH000706001103574000	3574	target Acadian - standoff near 25 cm
		3274MH000706001103575000	3575	target Acadian - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00709	Acadian stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3274MH000709001103576000	3576	autofocus sub-frame for target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3274MH000709001103577000	3577	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3274MH000709001103578000	3578	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3274MH000709001103579000	3579	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103580000	3580	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103581000	3581	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103582000	3582	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103583000	3583	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103584000	3584	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103585000	3585	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00709	Acadian stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3274MH000709001103586000	3586	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103587000	3587	autofocus sub-frame for target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3274MH000709001103588000	3588	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3274MH000709001103589000	3589	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3274MH000709001103590000	3590	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103591000	3591	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103592000	3592	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103593000	3593	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103594000	3594	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000709001103595000	3595	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00715	Acadian ~1 cm standoff	3274MH000715001103596000	3596	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103597000	3597	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103598000	3598	autofocus sub-frame for target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm
		3274MH000715001103599000	3599	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm
		3274MH000715001103600000	3600	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3274MH000715001103601000	3601	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103602000	3602	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103603000	3603	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103604000	3604	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103605000	3605	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00189	Focus Merges	3274MH000715001103606000	3606	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103607000	3607	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000715001103608000	3608	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3274MH000193001103609000	3609	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3274 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3601-3608 - best focus image product
		3274MH000193001103610000	3610	target Acadian - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3274 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3601-3608 - range map product
		3274MH000193001103611000	3611	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3274 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3590-3597 - best focus image product
mhl00189	Focus Merges	3274MH000193001103612000	3612	target Acadian - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3274 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3590-3597 - range map product
		3274MH000193001103613000	3613	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3274 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3579-3586 - best focus image product
		3274MH000193001103614000	3614	target Acadian - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3274 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3579-3586 - range map product

updated: 25_October_2021

Sol 3277 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Oct-21
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3276 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	3277MH001530001103672R00	3672	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3664-3671 - best focus image product
		3277MH001530001103673S00	3673	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3664-3671 - range map product
		3277MH001530001103674R00	3674	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3653-3660 - best focus image product
		3277MH001530001103675S00	3675	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3653-3660 - range map product
		3277MH001530001103676R00	3676	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3636-3643 - best focus image product
		3277MH001530001103677S00	3677	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3636-3643 - range map product
		3277MH001530001103678R00	3678	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3625-3632 - best focus image product
		3277MH001530001103679S00	3679	target Jopps_Salt - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3276 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3625-3632 - range map product

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3278 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Oct-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Wardie and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Wardie ~25 cm standoff	3278MH0001900001103680C00	3680	autofocus sub-frame for target Wardie - standoff near 25 cm
		3278MH0001900001103681C00	3681	target Wardie - standoff near 25 cm
mN002299	Wardie stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3278MH0002990001103682C00	3682	autofocus sub-frame for target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3278MH0002990001103683C00	3683	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3278MH0002990001103684C00	3684	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103685C00	3685	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103686C00	3686	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103687C00	3687	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103688C00	3688	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103689C00	3689	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103690C00	3690	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103691C00	3691	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002299	Wardie stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3278MH0002990001103692C00	3692	autofocus sub-frame for target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3278MH0002990001103693C00	3693	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3278MH0002990001103694C00	3694	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103695C00	3695	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103696C00	3696	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103697C00	3697	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103698C00	3698	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103699C00	3699	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103700C00	3700	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3278MH0002990001103701C00	3701	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002025	Focus Merges	3278MH0002650001103702N00	3702	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3278 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3694-3701 - best focus image product
		3278MH0002650001103703S00	3703	target Wardie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3278 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3694-3701 - range map product
		3278MH0002650001103704N00	3704	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3278 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3684-3693 - best focus image product
		3278MH0002650001103705S00	3705	target Wardie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3278 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3684-3693 - range map product

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3279 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Oct-21
camera positions	4
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	41

MAHLI imaged the target Ashlar and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00705	Ashlar ~25 cm standoff	3279MH000706001103706C00	3706	autofocus sub-frame for target Ashlar - standoff near 25 cm
		3279MH000706001103707C00	3707	target Ashlar - standoff near 25 cm
		3279MH000706001103708C00	3708	target Ashlar - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00705	Ashlar stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3279MH000763001103709C00	3709	autofocus sub-frame for target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3279MH000763001103710C00	3710	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3279MH000763001103711C00	3711	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3279MH000763001103712C00	3712	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103713C00	3713	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103714C00	3714	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103715C00	3715	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103716C00	3716	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103717C00	3717	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103718C00	3718	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000763001103719C00	3719	target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mhl00705	Ashlar stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3279MH000763001103720C00
3279MH000763001103721C00	3721			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3279MH000763001103722C00	3722			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3279MH000763001103723C00	3723			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103724C00	3724			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103725C00	3725			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103726C00	3726			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103727C00	3727			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103728C00	3728			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103729C00	3729			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3279MH000763001103730C00	3730			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00705	Ashlar ~1 cm standoff			3279MH000785001103731C00
		3279MH000785001103732C00	3732	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm
		3279MH000785001103733C00	3733	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3279MH000785001103734C00	3734	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103735C00	3735	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103736C00	3736	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103737C00	3737	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103738C00	3738	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103739C00	3739	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103740C00	3740	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3279MH000785001103741C00	3741	target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mhl00189	Focus Merges	3279MH000193001103742R00
3279MH000193001103743S00	3743			target Ashlar - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3279 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3734-3741 - range map product
3279MH000193001103744R00	3744			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3279 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3723-3730 - best focus image product
3279MH000193001103745S00	3745			target Ashlar - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3279 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3723-3730 - range map product
3279MH000193001103746R00	3746			target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3279 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3712-3719 - best focus image product
3279MH000193001103747S00	3747			target Ashlar - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3279 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3712-3719 - range map product

updated: 29_October_2021

Sol 3280 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Oct-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Rhue and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Rhue ~25 cm standoff	3280MH00706001103748C0D	3748	autofocus sub-frame for target Rhue - standoff near 25 cm
		3280MH00706001103749C0D	3749	target Rhue - standoff near 25 cm
		3280MH00706001103750C0D	3750	target Rhue - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00763	Rhue stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3280MH00763001103751C0D	3751	autofocus sub-frame for target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3280MH00763001103752C0D	3752	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3280MH00763001103753C0D	3753	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3280MH00763001103754C0D	3754	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103755C0D	3755	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103756C0D	3756	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103757C0D	3757	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103758C0D	3758	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103759C0D	3759	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103760C0D	3760	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3280MH00763001103761C0D	3761	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00763	Rhue stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3280MH00763001103762C0D
3280MH00763001103763C0D	3763			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3280MH00763001103764C0D	3764			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3280MH00763001103765C0D	3765			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103766C0D	3766			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103767C0D	3767			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103768C0D	3768			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103769C0D	3769			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103770C0D	3770			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103771C0D	3771			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3280MH00763001103772C0D	3772			target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges			3280MH002650001103773R0D
		3280MH002650001103774S0D	3774	target Rhue - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3765-3772 - range map product
		3280MH002650001103775R0D	3775	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3754-3761 - best focus image product
		3280MH002650001103776S0D	3776	target Rhue - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3754-3761 - range map product

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3283 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21-Oct-21	
		camera positions	51	Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		total parent images	4	CDPID:
		focus merges performed	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total focus merge products	8	
		total parent images + focus merge products	59	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Isle_of_Mists and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Isle_of_Mists before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3283MH0001900001103777C00	3777	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3283MH000190001103778C00	3778	target Isle_of_Mists - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00212	Isle_of_Mists before DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3283MH000120001103779C00	3779	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000120001103780C00	3780	target Isle_of_Mists - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00706	Isle_of_Mists after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3283MH0007060001103781C00	3781	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3283MH000706001103782C00	3782	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3283MH0007060021103783C00	3783	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00763	Isle_of_Mists after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3283MH0007630001103784C00	3784	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000763001103785C00	3785	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000763001103786C00	3786	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3283MH000763001103787C00	3787	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103788C00	3788	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103789C00	3789	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103790C00	3790	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103791C00	3791	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103792C00	3792	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103793C00	3793	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103794C00	3794	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103795C00	3795	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000763001103796C00	3796	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000763001103797C00	3797	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00763	Isle_of_Mists after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3283MH000763001103798C00	3798	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103799C00	3799	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103800C00	3800	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103801C00	3801	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103802C00	3802	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103803C00	3803	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103804C00	3804	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103805C00	3805	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000740001103806C00	3806	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3283MH00074001103807C00	3807	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3283MH00074001103808C00	3808	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3283MH000740021103809C00	3809	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000740031103810C00	3810	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000740031103811C00	3811	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3283MH000740031103812C00	3812	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3283MH000740031103813C00	3813	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3283MH000740031103814C00	3814	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3283MH000740031103815C00	3815	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3283MH000740031103816C00	3816	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00763	Isle_of_Mists after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3283MH000763001103817C00	3817	autofocus sub-frame for target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000763001103818C00	3818	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3283MH000763001103819C00	3819	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3283MH000763001103820C00	3820	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103821C00	3821	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103822C00	3822	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103823C00	3823	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103824C00	3824	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103825C00	3825	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103826C00	3826	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH000763001103827C00	3827	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3283MH0001530001103828R00	3828	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3820-3827 - best focus image product
		3283MH0001530001103829R00	3829	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3820-3827 - range map product
		3283MH0001530001103830R00	3830	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3809-3816 - best focus image product
3283MH0001530001103831R00	3831	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3809-3816 - range map product		
3283MH0001530001103832R00	3832	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3798-3805 - best focus image product		
3283MH0001530001103833R00	3833	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3798-3805 - range map product		
3283MH0001530001103834R00	3834	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3787-3794 - best focus image product		
3283MH0001530001103835R00	3835	target Isle_of_Mists - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3283 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3787-3794 - range map product		

updated: 02_November_2021

Sol 3284 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	2-Nov-21	
camera positions:	2	Image ID:
total parent images:	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:
total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products:	2	

summary of MAHLI activities:	MAHLI imaged the REMS UV Sensor.
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Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00095	REMS UV sensor *15 cm standoff	3284MH000095001103836CDD	3836	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3284MH000095001103837CDD	3837	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation

updated: 03_November_2021

Sol 3285 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	2-Nov-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Dornoch_Beach and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00705	Dornoch_Beach ~25 cm standoff	3285MH0007060001103838C0D	3838	autofocus sub-frame for target Dornoch_Beach - standoff near 25 cm
		3285MH0007060011103839C0D	3839	target Dornoch_Beach - standoff near 25 cm
		3285MH0007060021103840C0D	3840	target Dornoch_Beach - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00699	Dornoch_Beach stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	3285MH000699001103841C0D	3841	autofocus sub-frame for target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3285MH0006990021103842C0D	3842	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3285MH0006990031103843C0D	3843	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3285MH0006990041103844C0D	3844	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH0006990051103845C0D	3845	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH0006990061103846C0D	3846	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH0006990071103847C0D	3847	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH0006990081103848C0D	3848	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH0006990091103849C0D	3849	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH0006990101103850C0D	3850	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3285MH000699011103851C0D	3851	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mhl00699	Dornoch_Beach stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	3285MH000699001103852C0D
3285MH0006990021103853C0D	3853			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
3285MH0006990031103854C0D	3854			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
3285MH0006990041103855C0D	3855			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH0006990051103856C0D	3856			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH0006990061103857C0D	3857			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH0006990071103858C0D	3858			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH0006990081103859C0D	3859			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH0006990091103860C0D	3860			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH0006990101103861C0D	3861			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3285MH000699011103862C0D	3862			target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00703	Focus Merges			3285MH0007030001103863R0D
		3285MH0007030002103864S0D	3864	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3285 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3855-3862 - range map product
		3285MH0007030003103865R0D	3865	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3285 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3844-3851 - best focus image product
		3285MH0007030004103866S0D	3866	target Dornoch_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3285 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3844-3851 - range map product

updated: 10_November_2021

Sol 3286 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	3-Nov-21
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	27

MAHLI imaged the target Dumbuck and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00706	Dumbuck ~25 cm standoff	3286MH0007060001103867C0D	3867	autofocus sub-frame for target Dumbuck - standoff near 25 cm
		3286MH000706001103868C0D	3868	target Dumbuck - standoff near 25 cm
		3286MH0007060021103869C0D	3869	target Dumbuck - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00182	Dumbuck stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3286MH0001820001103870C0D	3870	autofocus sub-frame for target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3286MH000182001103871C0D	3871	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3286MH0001820021103872C0D	3872	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820031103873C0D	3873	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820041103874C0D	3874	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820051103875C0D	3875	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820061103876C0D	3876	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820071103877C0D	3877	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820081103878C0D	3878	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820091103879C0D	3879	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00182	Dumbuck stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3286MH0001820001103880C0D	3880	autofocus sub-frame for target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3286MH000182001103881C0D	3881	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3286MH0001820021103882C0D	3882	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820031103883C0D	3883	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820041103884C0D	3884	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820051103885C0D	3885	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820061103886C0D	3886	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820071103887C0D	3887	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820081103888C0D	3888	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3286MH0001820091103889C0D	3889	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00265	Focus Merges	3286MH0002650001103890R0D	3890	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3286 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3882-3889 - best focus image product
		3286MH0002650001103891S0D	3891	target Dumbuck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3286 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3882-3889 - range map product
		3286MH0002650001103892R0D	3892	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3286 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3872-3879 - best focus image product
		3286MH0002650001103893S0D	3893	target Dumbuck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3286 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3872-3879 - range map product

updated: 08_November_2021

Sol 3287 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4 Nov 21
camera position	45
total parent images	4
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	37

MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Zechstein after DRT and a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mnh00705	Zechstein after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3287MH0007060001103894C00	3894	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3287MH000706001103895C00	3895	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		3287MH0007060021103896C00	3896	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3287MH000706003103897C00	3897	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
mnh00703	Zechstein after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3287MH000706001103898C00	3898	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3287MH0007060021103899C00	3899	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3287MH0007060031103900C00	3900	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060041103901C00	3901	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060051103902C00	3902	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060061103903C00	3903	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060071103904C00	3904	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060081103905C00	3905	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060091103906C00	3906	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0007060101103907C00	3907	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mnh00703	Zechstein after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3287MH000706001103908C00	3908	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3287MH0007060021103909C00	3909	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3287MH0007060031103910C00	3910			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3287MH0007060041103911C00	3911			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060051103912C00	3912			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060061103913C00	3913			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060071103914C00	3914			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060081103915C00	3915			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060091103916C00	3916			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060101103917C00	3917			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH000706011103918C00	3918			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mnh00801	Zechstein after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff			3287MH000800001103919C00	3919	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3287MH0008000021103920C00	3920	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm		
		3287MH0008000031103921C00	3921	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3287MH0008000041103922C00	3922	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0008000051103923C00	3923	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0008000061103924C00	3924	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0008000071103925C00	3925	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0008000081103926C00	3926	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0008000091103927C00	3927	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH0008000101103928C00	3928	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3287MH000800011103929C00	3929	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mnh00703	Zechstein after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3287MH000706001103930C00	3930	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
3287MH0007060021103931C00	3931			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
3287MH0007060031103932C00	3932			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3287MH0007060041103933C00	3933			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060051103934C00	3934			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060061103935C00	3935			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060071103936C00	3936			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060081103937C00	3937			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060091103938C00	3938			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH0007060101103939C00	3939			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3287MH000706011103940C00	3940			intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mnh00405	Zechstein after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff			3287MH0004050001103941C00	3941	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3287 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3287MH000405001103942C00	3942	intended Zechstein drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3287 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm		
mnh000153	Focus Merges	3287MH0001530001103943R00	3943	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3933-3940 - best focus image product		
		3287MH0001530001103944R00	3944	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3933-3940 - range map product		
		3287MH0001530001103945R00	3945	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3922-3929 - best focus image product		
		3287MH0001530001103946R00	3946	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3922-3929 - range map product		
		3287MH0001530001103947R00	3947	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3911-3918 - best focus image product		
		3287MH0001530001103948R00	3948	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3911-3918 - range map product		
		3287MH0001530001103949R00	3949	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3900-3907 - best focus image product		
		3287MH0001530001103950R00	3950	intended Zechstein drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3287 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3900-3907 - range map product		

updated: 08_November_2021

Sol 3289 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		Drill preparation activities at the planned Zechstein sample extr action site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Zechstein sample discard pile and the intended Zechstein portion sites one and two.		
acquired/performed date(s)	0-Nov-21	Image ID:		
camera position:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
total parent images:	0	CDPID:		
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total focus merge products:	0			
total parent images + focus merge products:	0			
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	Intended Zechstein Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~25 cm standoff	3289MH00190001103951C00	3951	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm
		3289MH00190001103952C00	3952	intended Zechstein drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm
mN002197	Intended Zechstein Drill Sample Portion Site One ~25 cm standoff	3289MH00197001103953C00	3953	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill sample portion site one - before drill attempt - standoff near 25 cm
		3289MH00197001103954C00	3954	intended Zechstein drill sample portion site one - before drill attempt - standoff near 25 cm
mN002197	Intended Zechstein Drill Sample Portion Site Two ~25 cm standoff	3289MH00197001103955C00	3955	autofocus sub-frame for intended Zechstein drill sample portion site two - before drill attempt - standoff near 25 cm
		3289MH00197001103956C00	3956	intended Zechstein drill sample portion site two - before drill attempt - standoff near 25 cm

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) values in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the -X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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